

MooringSense – GA 851703

Mooring System Integrity Management through Monitoring, Digital Twin and Control Technologies for Cost Reduction and Increased Efficiency

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Mooring System Integrity Management Technologies

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Executive Summary

The MooringSense project aims to reducing OPEX and increasing efficiency of FOWT through the development of efficient risk-based integrity management strategies for mooring systems based on a cost effective and reliable on-line monitoring technology and digital twin.

This deliverable provides an overview of the state-of-the-art of current technologies, tools and techniques related to integrity management of mooring systems currently applied to the O&G industry, from the perspective of FOW, with the aim of identifying the technological gaps applied to the integrity management of mooring systems.

In the first instance, it shall be highlighted that the purpose of a mooring system in both O&G and FOW is station keeping, namely to keep a floating structure within reasonable proximity of a designated location and to avoid excessive movement that will hinder safe operation.

In the O&G industry, mooring systems have been utilized for many years and there is a level of understanding of vessel motion and wave interaction that is significantly higher compared to the concepts employed by the floating offshore renewables sector. Although this can be seen as a weakness, the FOW industry can leverage the O&G experience to ensure that reliable and cost-effective solutions are employed.

However, a key difference when comparing a mooring system for a traditional O&G installation (i.e. a semisubmersible or an FPSO) and a FOW farm is in the number of mooring lines. A traditional O&G installation will generally comprise of a limited number of mooring lines (i.e.10-30); however, for a medium size FOW of 50 FOWT, each turbine will have 3 to 6 mooring with a total number in the range of 150-300. Given the high cost of offshore operations (inspection, maintenance, repairs) it is of vital importance that a cost-effective integrity management strategy is implemented to keep OPEX at an acceptable level.

This deliverable details the key aspect related to integrity management of mooring system including degradation mechanism in chain, wire ropes and synthetic ropes; inspection and integrity management techniques; failure detection, line tension monitoring, control algorithms and digital twin. In addition, the deliverables highlight some technological gaps, which are summarised below:

- With regards to international standards and guidelines, there is a clear need for tailored documentation focusing on the challenges of FOW and, in particular, there is the need of a tailored risk-based approach that can be applied to the FOW industry to enhance the effective operation of the floating structures whilst reducing costs.
- SHM for monitoring the integrity of FOW substructures is in the development phase. First systems are available on the market, but there are reasonable doubts regarding their reliability and robustness, and local inspection remains necessary for making decisions on O&M. Effective mooring line failure detection systems are still required.
- Work on the exploitation of novel sensors such as those proposed in this project is not abundant, for obvious reasons. More generally, the relationship between turbine control, platform position and mooring line loads requires careful study.
- Several monitoring technologies are available today to provide mooring line tension measurements in floating platform as a source of information for integrity assessment and management. However, these technologies present several issues related to robustness and reliability, as well as costs if they are to be applied to FOW, where long term operation and low cost are mandatory requirements
- Designing and implementing a Digital Twin of a mooring line requires simultaneous adoption of several technologies and tools. Some of these technologies are still at early stage of development however are evolving at fast pace.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Term	Description
ABS	American Bureau of Shipping
ADCP	Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler
AET	Acoustic Emissions Testing
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALARP	As Low as Reasonably Possible
API	American Petroleum Institute
ARIMA	Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average
CAE	Computer Aided Engineering
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CMS	Chain Measurement System
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
CoF	Consequence of Failure
COTS	Commercial Off-the-shelf
CPC	Collective Pitch Control
CVI	Closer Visual Inspection
DAC	Disturbance Accommodating Control
DMS	Data Management System
DP	Dynamic Positioning
DT	Digital Twin
DVI	Detailed Visual Inspection
FBG	Fibre Bragg Gratings
FEM	Finite Element Methods
FFS	Fitness for Service
FoS	Factor of Safety
FOW	Floating Offshore Wind
FOWF	Floating Offshore Wind Farm
FOWT	Floating Offshore Wind Turbine
FPS	Floating Production System
FPSO	Floating Production Storage and Offloading

FPU	Floating Production Unit
FWT	Floating Wind Turbine
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GS	Gain Scheduling
GVI	General Visual Inspection
HMPE	High Modulus Polyethylene
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
IM	Integrity Management
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
IT	Information Technology
JIP	Joint Industry Project
LF	Low Frequency
LQR	Linear Quadratic Regulator
LPV	Linear Parameter Varying
MBS	Maximum Break Strength
MEMS	Micro Electro-Mechanical System
MFL	Magnetic Flux Leakage
MIC	Microbiologically Induced Corrosion
MIM	Mooring Integrity Management
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
MODU	Mobile Offshore Drilling Unit
MPI	Magnetic Particle Inspection
NDT	Non-Destructive Testing
NMPZ	Non-Minimum Phase Zeros
O&G	Oil and Gas
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
OPB	Out-of-Plane Bending
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
OREI	Offshore Renewable Energy Installations
P&ID	Piping and Instrumentation Diagram
PD	Proportional and Derivative

PE	Polyethylene
PI	Process Information
PI	Proportional and Integral
PoF	Probability of Failure
PPP	Precision Point Positioning
QTF	Quadratic Transfer Functions
RBF	Radial Basis Function
RBI	Risk-Based Inspection
RMS	Rope Measurement System
ROV	Remotely Operated Vehicle
RP	Recommended Practice
RTK	Real Time Kinematics
SAMIR	Semi-Autonomous Mooring Inspection Robot
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SF	State Feedback
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
SPM	Single Point Mooring
SRB	Sulphate Reducing Bacteria
SS	State Space
TLP	Tension Leg Platform
TSA	Thermal Spray Aluminium
TSC	Tungsten Spray Carbide
TTR	Time To Rupture
UT	Ultrasonic Testing

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

The objective of this report is to analyse the state-of-the-art of current technologies, tools and techniques related to integrity management of mooring system currently applied to the O&G industry, from the perspective of FOW, with the aim of identifying the technological gaps applied to the integrity management of mooring systems.

The focus will be on degradation and damage in main mooring components like chains, wire ropes and synthetic ropes, failure detection systems, line tension monitoring, inspection methods and tools, digital twin and integrity management strategies of mooring lines and FOW.

1.2 Intended audience / Classification

This is a public deliverable, thus the document is intended for all interested readers

1.3 Application documents

Inputs from the following documents were used as a source of information for preparing this document:

Table 1: Application documents

REF	Document
AD-01	Grant Agreement – 851703 – MooringSense
AD-02	Consortium Agreement – MooringSense

1.4 Document structure

The document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 provides general background information regarding mooring system for O&G and FOW assets
- Section 3 provides an overview of degradation mechanisms and damage prevention in mooring chains
- Section 4 provides an overview of degradation mechanisms in mooring chains and wire ropes
- Section 5 provides details of current practices with regards to integrity management of mooring lines and an overview of inspection technologies and tools.
- Section 6 provides details of failure detection and structural health monitoring (SHM)
- Section 7 provides details of closed loop turbine controls algorithms
- Section 8 describes line tension monitoring technologies
- Section 9 provides information regarding digital twin

2. Background

2.1 General

Carbon neutral energy is quickly becoming a necessity. Currently, electricity generation accounts for in excess of 40% of CO₂ emissions globally. This has led for a greater push towards preparing the renewable energy industry to take the burden from the power generation industry which is heavily dependent on fossil fuels. Although advancements are being made in all the renewable energy forms, there is an apparent bias towards wind energy in Europe, with both onshore and offshore accounting for 15% of the market share. In order to continue the progression of the wind sector, it is vital to take full advantage of the potential energy available, to do this, turbines should be located in regions with stronger and more consistent winds. There is an abundance of areas with such characteristics in the seas of Europe as Figure 1 depicts. This consequently has raised the issue of water depth and the capabilities of the various foundation types for conventional offshore wind structures, see Table 2.

Figure 1: Mean Wind Speed in Europe [1].

Table 2: Operational depths of various wind turbine foundations [2]

Foundation type	Operational depth
Monopile	< 15m
Gravity	≤ 30m
Jacket	30m - 50m

Figure 2 - Offshore Wind turbine Structures [3]

With the conventional methods of securing offshore wind energy being unusable at certain water depths, either a new and innovative solution is required or a glance over to the success the O&G industry has had in deep water.

Floating Offshore Wind (FOW) aim at providing a cost-effective solution by leveraging learnings from the O&G industry. The structure types listed in Table 3 are currently used in the FOW industry.

Table 3: FOW Structures

Type	Advantages	Disadvantages
Spar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simple design that can be easily fabricated Minimum number of welds Possibility of using concrete instead of steel Few active systems or complicated components Excellent stability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Only suitable for deep water sites (>80m) due to a large draft Assembly in shallow water not possible Limited ability to tow the structure back to port for major repairs Requires large drafts for onshore assemblies
Semi-Submersible and Barge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Most flexible designs with regards to water depth Can be assembled onshore and towed to the final position Can be easily towed back for maintenance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Might have larger wave induced motions that may impact the rotor, tower and blades Semi-subs are based on complex structures, more difficult to manufacture. However, barge designs usually have a simple shape that would employ equally simple fabrication techniques that are well established. Requires comparably large amounts of steel Might be more subject to corrosion and ice-loads since much of the structure is closer to the water surface Large facilities for onshore assembly required (dry-dock)

Tension- Leg- Platform (TLP)	Low structural mass and material usage Can be assembled onshore and towed to the final position Few moving parts (no active ballast required) Excellent stability Lower fatigue loads in tower and blades than semi-submersible structures and lower fatigue loads in the tower base than Spar-Buoys Simple structure to inspect Few active systems and components	High loads on the mooring and anchoring system Concerns about the lifetime of tendons Difficult installation process, due to inherent instability during the towing Often requires specialised installation vessels Less developed concept for wind energy applications
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Figure 3: Floating Offshore Wind concepts - WindEurope

Today, the total globally installed capacity of floating offshore wind power is around 80 MW, (Table 4). A number of prototypes or demo projects were installed between 2009 and 2018, which have demonstrated the viability of different technologies. Then, Hywind Scotland Pilot Project, installed in 2017, was the first pre-commercial floating wind park with 5 large turbines of 6MW in array formation. Wind Float Atlantic was the second Pilot Project, being the turbines of 8.4 MW the largest ever installed on a floating platform.

Table 4: Installed FOW Projects

Project	Date	Location	Substructure	Technology	Developer	Turbine Capacity	Total Capacity
Kinkardine	2009	Norway	Spar	Statoil	Statoil	2.3 MW	2.3 MW
WindFloat	2011	Portugal	Semi-submersible	Principle Power	EDPR	2 MW	2 MW
Kabashima	2013	Japan	Hybrid Spar	Toda	Toda Corp.	2 MW	2 MW
Fukushima	2013	Japan	Semi-submersible	Mitsui	Marubeni	2 MW	2 MW
Fukushima	2016	Japan	V-Shape Semi-sub	Mitsubishi	Marubeni	7 MW	7 MW
Fukushima	2016	Japan	Advanced Spar	Japan Marine United	Marubeni	5 MW	5 MW
Hywind Scotland	2017	UK	Spar	Statoil	Statoil	6 MW (x5)	30 MW
Floatgen	2018	France	Barge	Ideol	Ideol	2 MW	2 MW
Nedo	2018	Japan	Barge	Ideol	Hitatzi Zosen	3 MW	3 MW
Windfloat Atlantic	2019	Portugal	Semi-submersible	Principal Power	Windplus	8.4. MW (x3)	25 MW

There are additional Pilot and Demo Projects to come, the majority in Europe, which will increase the total installed capacity up to around 300 MW during next years.

Table 5: Upcoming FOW Projects

Project	Date	Location	Substructure	Technology	Developer	Turbine Capacity	Total Capacity
Kinkardine	2020	UK	Semi-submersible	Principle Power	Cobra	9.5 MW (x5) + 2 MW (x1)	50 MW
Hywind Tampen	2021	Norway	Hybrid Spar	Equinor	Equinor	8 MW (x11)	88 MW
Goto	2021	Japan	Hybrid Spar	Toda	Toda	2 MW (x8) + 5MW (x1)	21 mW
Demo SATH	2021	Spain	Twin Hull	Saitec Offshore	Saitec	2 MW	2 MW
TetraSpar	2021	Norway	TetraSpar	Stiesdal	Stiesdal	3.6 2MW	3.6 MW
Groix	2022	France	Semi-submersible	Naval Energies	Eolfi	9.5 MW (x3)	28.5 MW
Leucate	2022	France	Semi-submersible	Principle Power	Engie	10 MW (x3)	30 MW
EolMed	2022	France	Barge	Ideol	Quadran	10 MW (x3)	30 MW
Provence Grand Large	2022	France	TLP	SBM	EDF	8 MW (x3)	24 MW

With the current and forecasted growth of the FOW sector, having reliable and dependable station keeping systems are key in for the security of the market. However, due to greater OPEX found/expected in the FOW industry due to a far greater number of mooring lines and mooring hardware than what is traditionally found on an O&G floating structure, a cost reduction solution is required. Thus, ensuring projects and commerce remain financially viable by reducing LCOE.

While research institutions have invested time and resources into understanding the dynamics and behaviour of mooring systems, there is still a clear gap in the implementation of the learnings as

premature failure is still a regularity [4],[5]. The UK's health and safety executive have classified mooring systems for FPU's as a critical component since mooring failure warrants shut down and can have direct consequences, both with regards to safety, environmentally and financially [6]. The same level of cruciality should be carried over to FOWT given the green nature and cost effective of the concept.

This deliverable reports on the state-of-the-art mooring technologies and practices revolving mooring systems, this is to include, materials, monitoring and inspection technologies and integrity management methodologies. In addition to this research into current level of industry knowledge and the operational challenges faced with mooring systems, this includes: the forms, effects and prevention methods for damage mechanisms in chains, synthetic ropes and wire ropes, inspection methods and tools, line tension monitoring and failure detection. Analysis of each is given with economic implications detailed, all from an FOW perspective.

2.2 Mooring Systems

Offshore mooring systems are usually comprised of several lines, composed by chain, wire or synthetic rope, tensioning equipment, and an anchoring system. Their core purpose is to maintain a floating structure on station within a safe predetermined tolerance. In addition to this, mooring systems are to aid in ensuring a safe working environment of personnel and allow for effective sustained operation. Mooring for the floating wind industry shares the same principles.

There are a number of different types of mooring systems available for floating structures in both O&G and FOW; catenary, taut leg, tension leg, single point, spread mooring and dynamic positioning, not all of the systems will be applicable to FOW due to the water depth limitations and associated costs.

2.2.1 Catenary System

Figure 4: Catenary System [7]

Catenary mooring systems take shape as free hanging lines, which are capable of providing restoring forces through the mass of the mooring lines and the change in the offshore structure's station. Catenary mooring lines terminate horizontally with anchoring directly in the seabed. They can be used in a wide range of offshore applications such as, deep and shallow waters, for FPU's and MODUs.

2.2.2 Taut leg System

Figure 5: Taut Leg System [7]

Taut leg mooring systems are characterised by the pre-tensioned mooring lines. Stiffness and elasticity of mooring lines is what provides the station keeping ability of this mooring system. With the lines typically having an angle of 30 to 45 degrees, the lines terminate at an acute angle. Taut leg is a cost-effective mooring solution for deep water.

2.2.3 Tension Leg Mooring

Figure 6: Tension Leg Mooring [8]

Tension leg mooring system consists of tubular steel legs, piled into the seabed and tensioned by the buoyancy of the floating structure. Horizontal movement is minimised due to the tension of the steel legs and the vertical nature of mooring system. Due to the stability, tension leg mooring can be found on several FPU's.

2.2.4 Single Point Mooring

Figure 7: Single point Mooring [10]

Single point mooring systems are apparent on floating vessels due to the ability of this mooring system to allow the vessel to weathervane 360 degrees according to the environmental conditions, this allows for the forces acting on the mooring lines to be minimised. This mooring system shares similarities with the tower yoke mooring system aside from the tower mooring requiring a structure fixed to the seabed.

2.2.5 Tower Yoke Mooring System

Figure 8 - Tower Yoke Mooring System [9]

The tower yoke mooring system, displayed in figure 7, is a form of single point mooring where a vessel moors to a fixed point referred to as the tower. The tower is fitted with roller bearing to allow the vessel to weathervane 360 degrees. This system is ideal for use in shallow waters.

2.2.6 Spread Mooring

Spread mooring systems are considered to be multi-point systems as they require multiple lines in a symmetrical pattern to ensure station keeping. Whether this is not possible due to the attachment to the floating structure. Water depth is not much of an issue for spread mooring making it a versatile system.

Figure 9: Spread Mooring [11]

2.3 Failures in mooring systems

There is a general consensus within class societies and the offshore industry that mooring is important for the effective functionality of offshore structures. These systems have been used within the O&G industry for many years. However, it has been well documented that issues still remain and failures are not uncommon. With long term mooring systems remaining in a sole location for lengthy periods of time, they are unable to be sheltered during extreme weather events, they are therefore designed to endure any condition they may face. Mooring systems are generally designed with adequate capacity to withstand design storm conditions. Historically, during the initial design stage, fatigue considerations have not always been included. Subsequently, over time, deterioration of lines makes single or multiple line failures more probable.

During the period between 2001 and 2011, a total of 21 separate mooring incidents which includes 9 major incidents occurred. They concluded that the annual probability of mooring system failure is on the order of 3×10^{-3} [12].

A variety of damage and failure mechanisms can be found, see sections 3 and 4.

Figure 10: Mooring failures [13]

Figure 10 displays where in the world failure has occurred. A point important to note is that the UK has seen a significant number of mooring failures off the coast of Scotland (North Sea), this is likely due to the harsh operating environment. With the North Sea being abundant in natural wind resources, ensuring mooring systems for FOW projects are at a sustainably high level is crucial for the success of the FOW industry.

Consequences of mooring failure range from risk to personnel, damage to risers, collisions, damage to cables, forced shutdowns and public relations damage. An example of this is the Gryphon Alpha floating production storage and offloading (FPSO) mooring failure in 2011, caused by a storm which produced 9m waves and 53 knot winds in the North Sea. Impromptu shut down and an evacuation of 74 non-essential personnel was carried out with only a skeleton crew remaining. It is reported that it cost approximately US\$1.8billion to reinstate [14].

Significant impact, both economic and environmental has been faced through unplanned maintenance or loss of hydrocarbons in the oil and gas industry. Therefore, there are a great deal of lessons to be learned for emerging industries such as FOW.

2.4 Differences and Similarities Between O&G and FOW

Although there are similarities with mooring for O&G and FOW, there are also some significant differences. FWT mooring requirements are not the same as in oil and gas. These differences can be explained by the smaller floater sizes, the wind turbine induced loads, shallower mooring depths and redundancy requirements.

A comparison between a typical floating structure from the O&G industry, Buchan Alpha and Hywind Scotland is given below in Table 5.

Table 6: Comparison between O&G and FOW floating structures [15]

Particulars	O&G - Buchan Alpha	FOW - Hywind Scotland
Installed	North Sea, 1981	North Sea, 2017
Substructure Type	Semi-Submersible	Spar-Buoy
Displacement	19,400t	12,000t
Draught	20-22m	75m
Water Depth	118m	95-120m
No. of Mooring lines	10	3 (per FOW turbine)
Line Length	3570m	900m
Breaking Strength	340t	2159t
Material	70mm 6x36 IWRC Wire	147mmØ Chain (60t weight)
Total Line Weight	715t	1200t
Anchors	Drag Embedment	Suction 16m x 5mØ, 300t

Notably, with O&G, the main trend has been to overengineer mooring components which results in high CAPEX. The added benefit of this is the reduced OPEX due to the less time requirements for inspection and maintenance. Furthermore, the level of understanding of vessel motion and wave interaction is significantly higher in traditional vessels compared to the concepts employed by the floating offshore renewables sector. This is partially affected by the inclusion of several moving components which induce cyclic loading in varying frequency ranges compared to the rigid floating structures of the oil and gas industry. An example of this is the additional thrust and torque loading that requires consideration. In addition to this, the purpose of mooring for both FOW and O&G remains the same.

2.5 Summary

Systems must be capable of enduring all damages and degradation mechanisms that can be derived from the environment; corrosion, marine growth, harsh conditions (storms). As expected, harsh operating conditions produce some of the greatest challenges for mooring systems and very little can be done besides considering such conditions during the project design phases. This has led to mooring systems having been identified as one of the key technical challenges with regards to FOW.

Significant efforts are currently underway to develop more effective and efficient methods of monitoring and inspecting mooring lines to detect early signs of degradation and to predict failure, to include line tension monitoring (see section 0), failure detection (see section 6) and integrity management/inspection (see section 5).

To allow FOW to become a global market, the issues facing unpredictable mooring failure must be addressed. This can come by means of increasing the understanding related to the loads, optimising the Integrity Management (IM), technologies and methods used to install, monitor and inspect mooring lines in-situ. Making use of the learnings from O&G through experience, best practices and technical standards then applying those which are deemed to be relevant to and benefit the FOW industry through improved performance and reduced CAPEX.

3. Degradation in Mooring Chains

3.1 Introduction

Chains have been used in the ship industry for many years and were first regulated in the mid-19th century by Lloyds Register of Shipping for classed ships. It must be noted that this category of chain, often called Marine Chain, is not a subject of this study as it is not used, nor recommended for offshore mooring applications. Thus, the word “chain” hereafter in the document, and throughout the MooringSense Project, refers to Offshore Mooring Chain, whose shape may appear similar to a Marine Chain but has substantial differences in terms of quality and performance.

Offshore Mooring Chains are widely used in temporary and permanent mooring systems for floating structures in the O&G and Floating Wind industries. There are two main types of chain link designs: stud and studless, both of which are illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 11: Stud link (left). Studless link (right)

The strength of both link designs is the same for a given diameter, and preference is mostly driven by the application. Studded chains are commonly used in temporary moorings (e.g. drilling rigs), due to its small size (typically 70, 76, or 84 mm diameter). However, when it comes to permanent moorings, typically with a design life of in-excess of 20 years (e.g. FPU's or FOWTs), studless chains are always selected. Long-term mooring systems are designed to safely keep the position of large floating structures subject to relevant fatigue loading, degradation phenomena, and extreme environmental conditions during their operational lifetime. Thus, a mooring chain for this application tends to be large, and chain diameters greater than 160 mm are not unusual.

Chains may be used as the sole component in mooring lines, but it is often employed as part of a system combining chain and ropes (being it fibre or steel wire), specially above 300 m water depth. There are a number of reasons why chain is a popular choice in a system:

- It is rugged and less damage prone than steel wire and fibre rope when operating on deck hardware or seabed.
- It is easier to handle and requires smaller deck tension equipment than a wire rope.
- Chain weight per unit length is higher than wire rope for a given strength providing larger catenary effect and weight at seabed so that a smaller anchor may be employed.
- Chain is intrinsically “torque balanced”, in that an axial load does not generate twist or torsional moments in a straight chain.
- It provides large flexibility during transport, pre-lay and hook-up of mooring systems.

Chains are made of different steel grades on a large range of diameters, hence covering a wide range of strengths. The following figure shows the strength of chains as a function of diameter and offshore grades, namely R3, R3S, R4, R4S, R5 and R6 with increasing tensile strength.

Figure 12: Chain Minimum Breaking Load

While offshore mooring chain, and synthetic and wire ropes are the main components in mooring lines, connectors are always present in mooring systems to either join the different components to the floating structure, to the anchors, as well as between them. There is a variety of permanent or long-term mooring connectors, the main concepts being D-type, H-type shackles, triplates, Unijoints or sockets (steel rope terminations), which are normally tailor made or dimensioned in every project to connect whatever mooring components together.

These connectors are made of steel, and hence can experience same degradation phenomena as chain. However, they are often oversized, and have increased strength and fatigue capacity relative to the components to which they are joint. Thus, it is very unlikely that connectors experience failures, and due to this, they are not covered in this document.

3.2 Forms of Damage and Degradation

The following figure illustrates different locations along a mooring line and typical damage and prevailing degradation mechanisms.

Figure 13: Damage and degradation mechanisms on mooring chains depending on the location

3.2.1 Straight Tension Fatigue

Straight tension, or tension-tension fatigue is due to the action of the environment (waves, wind and current) on the floating structure and its moorings, causing cyclic variation of axial loads at wave and lower frequencies. It is normally the main damage mechanism in mooring chains, and often drives the design and consequently the selection of chain size and grade. At design stage, fatigue damage is computed using fatigue loads derived from mooring analysis, together specific SN fatigue curves for chains and methods in design codes.

The preferential hot spots for fatigue crack initiation on a chain link are the outer crown and the inner bend sections [19], as indicated in the stress distributions below.

Figure 14: Straight tension hot spots.

Figure 15: Examples of failing sections from fatigue tests [18].

3.2.2 Out-Of-Plane Bending Fatigue

Out-of-Plane bending (OPB) refers to the bending of a chain link out of its main plane due to the action of transverse forces and moments, that are resisted by frictional forces at interlink contact with its adjoining link. When the axial load is high, chain links lock together working as beams up to certain bending moment threshold, above which they start to roll and slide against each other.

Figure 16: OPB mechanism [17].

Under high pretension, the interlink friction is high and the moment to be resisted at the contact between links can be significant. This rather unusual loading condition for a chain link arises from the combination of high tension load, and poor articulation at floater/line connecting point.

OPB phenomenon can preferably occur in the first link after a link that is restrained, e.g. by a chain stopper in the floating structure. In the following figure link 4 is sitting on a chain stopper, and it is link 5, the one that experiences the largest OPB loads, which decrease along the following links.

Figure 17: Chainhawse type connection to floating body [16]

The OPB fatigue hot spots are located at the bend section and out of the plane of the link as can be observed in the stress distribution in the figure below.

Figure 18: OPB Stress distribution

Alternating OPB stresses may be large enough to cause fatigue crack propagation and premature failure. This was the case of the Girasol deep water buoy, where 4 links failed in less than one year, always the first moving links of the failing lines [16].

3.2.3 Corrosion

Corrosion is defined as the deterioration of a material as a result of an electrochemical attack by its surroundings. It can also be understood as the tendency that materials have to find their most stable or lower internal energy form. The rate at which corrosion takes place will depend on the temperature, the salinity of the fluid in contact with the metal and the properties of the metals. Corrosion, therefore, is a gradual chemical attack on a metal, due to its environment, which results in the conversion of a metal into oxide, salt or some other compounds. Corrosive environments are generally given by air, industrial atmospheres, acidic, saline or basic solutions, soil, etc. In addition, the temperature significantly influences the magnitude of the corrosion. Metals that have suffered corrosion lose their mechanical properties, so they should generally be avoided or rather minimized. Corrosion's electrochemical attack is capable of destroying a metal structure by the action of numerous galvanic cells that form on its surface when said structure is immersed in a conductive aqueous medium (electrolyte).

For there to be an oxidation-reduction reaction there must be an element that yields electrons and another that accepts them.

- The reducing agent is the chemical element that supplies electrons of its chemical structure to the medium, increasing its oxidation state that is, oxidizing.
- The oxidizing agent is the chemical element that tends to capture these electrons being in a lower oxidation state than it had, that is, reduced.

Corrosion of iron or steel in the presence of oxygen is an electrochemical process. Thus, the place where the metal undergoes corrosion, where iron passes from the metallic to the ionic state, and then to the solution state, is called the anode. The anodic reaction can be written as follows:

The two electrons released in the anodic process move, through the metal mass, to the cathode or cathodic zone. In it, the two electrons are captured by the H⁺ ions present in the solution (electrolyte), which pass to atomic hydrogen (H), which is released as hydrogen gas molecules (H₂). The cathodic reaction can be written as follows:

We can summarize the above by saying that in order for corrosion to exist, certain minimum conditions must be met. These are:

1. There must be an anode and a cathode.
2. There must be an electrical potential between the two electrodes (anode and cathode).
3. There must be a metallic conductor that electrically connects the anode and cathode.
4. Both the anode and the cathode must be immersed in an electrolyte that conducts electricity, which is ionized.

For mooring chains, a corrosion allowance is to be considered in design, by increasing the chain diameter a given thickness per year over the intended service life. The following table shows minimum recommended values according to different design codes.

Table 7: Design Corrosion Rates

Code		Chain corrosion-wear allowance (mm/year)		
		Splash	Catenary	Bottom
DNVGL-OS-E301	No inspection	0.4	0.3	0.4
	Regular inspection	0.2	0.2	0.3
	Norwegian self	0.8	0.2	0.7
	Tropical waters	1.0	0.3	0.4
ISO 19901-7 2005		0.2-0.8	0.1-0.2	0.2-0.8
BV NR 493		0.4	0.3	0.4
API RP 2SK 2005		0.2-0.4	0.1-0.2	0.2-0.4

The main corrosion phenomena that affect chains are generalized corrosion, pitting corrosion and microbiologically influenced corrosion (MIC).

Corrosion mainly depends on water temperature, oxygenation, flow velocity and the presence of fouling or coral attacks in warmwater, which can induce MIC. Among them, water temperature, is the factor that has the largest influence on corrosion.

Figure 19: Corrosion rates with water temperature (left) and flow velocity (right)

3.2.3.1 General Corrosion

Generalized or uniform corrosion can be described as a corrosion reaction that occurs equally across the entire surface of the material, causing a general loss of metal. It extends homogeneously and the average penetration is the same at all points, hence being the most benign form of corrosion. It is the most common corrosive process among most metals and alloys, but in stainless steels it is very scarce due to its high chromium content that, in solution in martensite, ferrite or austenite, opposes the progression of corrosion.

Figure 20: General corrosion 17 years in service North Sea (cold water).

Figure 21: Chain attacked by sun corals in West Africa and cleaning in process [29]

3.2.3.2 Pitting Corrosion

It is highly localized, occurs in areas of low generalized corrosion and the anodic process (reaction) produces small "bites" in the body that affect. It can generally be observed on surfaces with little or almost no generalized corrosion. It occurs as a process of local anodic dissolution where metal loss is accelerated by the presence of a small anode and a much larger cathode.

Figure 22: Mild pitting in chain

Figure 23: Severe pitting in chain

Pitting corrosion develops only in the presence of aggressive anionic species and chlorine ions, although these factors are not the only ones. The severity of pitting tends to vary logarithmically with the chlorine concentration. Chlorine is an anion of a strong acid, and many metal cations show considerable solubility in chlorine solutions. This compound is a relatively small and highly diffusive anion, which interferes with natural passivity.

Pitting is considered as a process of autocatalytic nature, once the drilling begins to grow, the developed conditions are such that they promote the growth of the drilling. The cathodic and anodic reactions comprising corrosion are spatially separated during pitting. The immediate means of perforation tends to deplete cathode reactants such as oxygen, which allows cathodic reactions to develop in other parts of the exposed metal surface, where there is more concentration of reactants. In the area near the perforation, the concentration of metal cations and anionic species such as chlorine begins to increase, which electro-migrates to the perforation while maintaining the neutral charge due to the balance of charges associated with the concentration of the cation. The pH in the pits is low due to the hydrolysis of the cation and the absence of local cathodic reactions. The hydrochloric acid generated is very aggressive for almost all metals and therefore bites tend to spread.

Perforations often grow under the surface of the metal. The pores are often covered. This situation can make visual detection extremely difficult, knowledge of the severity of the attack can be overlooked and the probability of catastrophic failures increases.

Pitting requires an initiation period, but when it starts it increases its speed. Inclusions, structural heterogeneity and micro composition changes are the beginnings of pitting. Pit growth depends on the composition of the material, electrolyte concentration and electrical potential. The phenomenon of mass transfer, characteristics of pitting, influences the growth kinetics, through the concentration of electrolytes in the perforation.

Figure 24. Process of propagation of an environment in seawater

Pitting corrosion has some other derived forms:

- Friction Corrosion or Fretting: it is produced by the relatively small movement (such as a vibration) of 2 substances in contact, of which one or both are metals. This movement generates a series of pitting on the metal surface, which are hidden by corrosion products and are only visible when it is removed.
- Cavitation corrosion: it is produced by the formation and collapse of bubbles on the surface of the metal (in contact with a liquid). It is a phenomenon similar to what happens to the rear faces of ship propellers. It generates a series of honeycomb bites.
- Selective Corrosion: it is similar to the so-called De-Corrosion Corrosion, where pieces of zinc corrode and leave a layer similar to the primitive alloy. In this case, it is selective because it acts only on noble metals such as Silver-Copper or Copper-Gold. Perhaps the most harmful part of this kind of attacks is that the corrosion of the metal involved generates a layer that covers the bites and makes the corroded metal look as if it were not, so it is very easy to damage the metal by subjecting it to a mechanical force.

3.2.3.3 Microbiologically Induced Corrosion

The phenomenon known as microbiologically influenced corrosion (MIC) is a very complex process of great importance in metal systems in marine environments. In the case of chains, the phenomenon can occur due to sulfate reducing bacteria (SRB).

Figure 25: Preconditions for MIC development

Figure 26: Microbiologically influenced corrosion (MIC)

Figure 27: Sulphate reduction bacteria (SRB) involved in MIC

Sulfate reducing bacteria are responsible for the formation of SH_2 , which later reacts with the iron in the steel to produce molecular hydrogen. The latter penetrates the material causing its embrittlement.

The process of SH_2 formation is justified by changing the behavior of aerobic to anaerobic bacteria as explained below. Once bacteria are concentrated on the surface of the chain, a biofilm layer is formed that acts as an interface between water and steel (Figure 28). Within this biofilm, bacteria consume nutrients and multiply.

Figure 28: Biofilm formation.

The biofilm layer thickens. The moment bacteria run out of nutrients, they are no longer active (Figure 29). When oxygen is depleted anaerobic bacteria begins to multiply inside the biofilm, particularly in the area of contact with steel (Figure 29).

Figure 29: Thickening of the biofilm (left). Step to anaerobic behavior (right).

As a consequence of this whole process, the concentration of hydrogen sulfide (H_2S) increases in the environment of the submerged chain (Figure 30). This sulfide reacts by corroding the steel and forming molecular hydrogen according to the following reaction:

Figure 30: Evolution of H_2S concentration.

However, in the case of chains the microbiologically influenced corrosion process generated by sulfate reducing bacteria results in an increase in hydrogen absorbed by steel.

3.2.4 Wear

Wear can be defined as the progressive loss of material from surfaces subject to relative motion. Wear resistance is not an intrinsic property of the material, but a characteristic of it in a particular mechanism and environment in which it operates.

Wear can occur between adjoining links when are subjected to relative motions, i.e. interlink rotations. A typical spot for interlink wear is vessel-line interface, especially when fairleads (pocketed wheels) are used, and the floater is subject to large pitch and roll motions. The amount of wear depends on the axial load, and the amount and amplitude of the rotation cycles between consecutive links.

Figure 31: Chain on 7-pocket fairlead and interlink wear after 10 years in service

Interlink wear can also occur at the touchdown if the chain links are subject to continuous ups and downs leading to large interlink rotations. The use of clump weights attached to seabed chains also increases interlink rotations and interlink wear.

3.2.5 Mechanical Damage

Chains can be subjected to mechanical damage during transport, installation or while in service. Typical mechanical damages can occur due to impacts with other metallic parts. The following figure illustrates mechanical damage on a chain link at vessel interface, caused by continuous clashes with the inner surface of the trumpet.

Figure 32: Damaged chain link due to contact with inner trumpet

3.2.6 Loose/Lost studs

There is experience about studs getting loose after years in service due to the action of corrosion. When studs become loose or they are lost, the stress pattern in the link changes and the worst-case stress concentration factor changes location and is magnified.

Figure 33: Stud link Stress distribution. Left: stud in place. Right: stud loose or lost

The print that the stud leaves on the inner straight section of the link becomes the hottest spot for fatigue crack initiation. When the stud is loose or lost, the fatigue capacity of the stud link is reduced around 65% relative to a link with the stud in place, and around 50% relative to a studless link. Strength wise there is also some loss of capacity, and a significant reduction of stiffness.

Figure 34: stud chain recovered from a CALM buoy. Left: missing stud. Right: loose stud

3.3 Degradation and Damage Prevention

3.3.1 Out-Of-Plane Bending Fatigue

To minimize or eradicate the phenomenon, it is advisable to reduce the bending moments at floater/line interface by means of roll/pitch articulations with low friction bushings and long lever arms between first chain link and articulation points.

3.3.1.1 Fairlead Chain Stopper

This improved fairlead design allows for chain locking in a long pivoting stopper arm, greatly reducing wear and bending fatigue on the chain as long as roll and pitch motions are absorbed at the horizontal axis of the pivoting arm and not by a chain link.

Figure 35: Left: regular fairlead. Right: fairlead chain stopper

3.3.1.2 Unijoint type connection

When the chain is to be connected directly to the floater without tensioning equipment on deck, Unijoint type connections with low friction bushings can be used to reduce wear and out-of-plane bending fatigue on the first chain links.

Figure 36: Unijoint-type connection

3.3.2 Corrosion and wear

Mooring chain can be protected against corrosion and wear using coatings:

- Thermal Spray Aluminum (TSA) is melted aluminum sprayed at high speed and temperature on the surface of the link. It provides the best protection against corrosion with a durability of at least 15 years.

Figure 37: TSA coated chain

- Thermal Spray Carbide (TSC) is thermal sprayed carbide applied using high velocity oxy-fuel spray process. When applied at the interlink zone provides wear and erosion resistance.

Figure 38: TSC coated grip area

- Polymeric Coatings provide combined protection for corrosion, wear and MIC:
 - o **Ceramkote** is a ceramic epoxy paint providing excellent abrasion and corrosion protection.
 - o **Polipolyurethane** based coatings.

3.4 Summary

Mooring chain is a very mature and robust product, that is present in all permanent mooring systems, either alone or in combination with other mooring components. It is less prone to mechanical damage than other mooring components, and its mechanical behaviour is well understood. However, it is always desired to avoid damaging the chain during installation and in service to preserve its integrity during its lifetime. Its long-term response to corrosion in cold waters is very good, but accelerated corrosion due to MIC in warm waters is challenging, and requires larger corrosion allowances, or the use of corrosion mitigation methods.

4. Degradation in Synthetic and Wire Ropes

4.1 Introduction

The development of steel wire and synthetic fibre mooring ropes for permanent mooring systems has mainly been driven by the requirements of the oil and gas industry (e.g. [215] and [216]). However, the developments and knowledge gained in other industries, such as aquaculture, maritime, and single point mooring (SPM) offtake may also be relevant to the development of mooring lines for FWTs.

Steel and synthetic fibre ropes are composed of small parallel components which act together when a load is applied. A typical spiral strand steel wire rope may have several hundred individual wires, and a typical synthetic fibre rope may contain tens of millions of individual filaments. In contrast, whilst chains may also consist of several thousand components (links), these components are arranged in series and each link bears the tension in the mooring system.

Rope design considers not only the rope assembly (i.e. the arrangement of the components) but also the components (wires and yarns), the types and grades of materials used and the form of the components. Whilst the material and mechanical properties of steel and synthetic fibres are very different, advances in design, materials and production techniques has resulted in many shared degradation mechanisms.

Steel wire ropes have high axial stiffness, high strength and medium weight. Steel wire ropes are used in mooring systems where their weight or robustness is an advantage but where the weight of a full chain system is impractical. Synthetic fibre ropes are available in a number of materials and their strength and axial stiffness vary according to the material selected. However, all synthetic fibre materials are virtually weightless in water. Consequently, they do not form a catenary and rely on their own axial stiffness for compliance. Synthetic fibre ropes are used in mooring systems where a significant weight saving, or the compliance of low axial stiffness materials is required.

Table 8: Indicative properties of steel and synthetic mooring ropes

	Synthetic fibre rope (polyester)	Spiral strand rope (steel)
MBL (tonnes)	1000	1000
Diameter (mm)	195	96
Linear weight in air (kg/m)	22	46
Linear weight in water (kg/m)	6	39
Static stiffness (x MBL)	15	85

Steel wire ropes used in permanent mooring are most commonly of spiral strand design and are manufactured from high tensile steel wires, approximately twice as strong as the material used to form chains. For long term mooring systems, spiral strand ropes usually include a plastic outer sheath to minimise corrosion and protect the rope from external damage.

Figure 39. Steel wire ropes: Left: multi strand. Centre: sheathed spiral strand. Right: six-strand

Figure 40. Typical synthetic fibre (left) and steel (right) mooring ropes

Synthetic fibre ropes used in mooring are most commonly of parallel sub-rope construction and include an integrated outer jacket and filter system. Following the pioneering work of Petrobras and Cesar del Vecchio in the early 1990s [211], polyester became the preferred material for oil and gas mooring systems. Polyester was selected because its combination of axial stiffness, strength and fatigue characteristics resulted in the lowest cost for deep water (e.g. 1000m or more) oil and gas mooring systems. However, in recent years polyester mooring systems have been developed for increasingly shallow water with some systems now deployed in less than 100m water depth. For FWT applications, other synthetic fibre materials are increasingly considered as an alternative to polyester. For taut moored FWTs, the lower axial stiffness of nylon may be attractive [217] whilst for TLP and modified catenary systems, high modulus materials such as HMPE, aramid or carbon fibres are all alternatives to steel components.

Figure 41: Synthetic fibre ropes

Both spiral strand and parallel sub-rope constructions are optimised for strength and tension fatigue and, asides from the large radius bends formed in a catenary, are not normally considered suitable for regular bending (e.g. around fairleads, sheaves or winches). Consequently, both spiral strand and parallel sub-rope constructions used in mooring systems, rely on another mooring line type (most commonly chain) at the top and bottom of the systems to facilitate bending. In other mooring applications (e.g. MODU mooring) stranded steel wire ropes are often used in conjunction with mooring fairleads and winches as an alternative to top chain.

4.2 Forms of Damage and Degradation

4.2.1 External Damage (Abrasion, Cutting and Wear)

External damage is the most common cause of significant degradation (i.e. requiring repair or replacement) in mooring ropes [218][219]. External damage can be caused by abrasion, cutting and crushing. Common sources include contact with other mooring system components (particularly chains), contact with sub-sea operations equipment (e.g. ROVs or work wires), contact with fishing gear and contact with installation equipment.

External damage to ropes can be divided into three categories; complete destruction of the load bearing part of the rope, partial destruction of the load bearing part of the rope and damage to the non-load bearing outer parts of the rope. Where the load bearing part of the rope is completely damaged or destroyed, repairs are usually impossible. In the case of partial damage to the load bearing part of the rope, although repairs are still usually impossible, it is often possible to operate the rope for a limited period of time whilst a replacement is organised. DNVGL have published a methodology for synthetic fibre ropes to document this approach [212] and a similar approach forms the basis of most steel wire rope discard criteria. The most common type of external damage to mooring ropes is to the outer jacket/sheath. Although this type of damage is often repairable, and does not immediately impact rope strength, this damage can have a significant impact on rope integrity as it can lead quickly to further damage to the load bearing parts of the rope. For example, corrosion in the case of steel ropes or particles ingress in the case of synthetic fibre ropes.

4.2.2 Corrosion

Like all steel components, steel ropes can suffer from corrosion. The effect of corrosion on steel wire rope is similar to chain in that metallic area is lost, leading to a loss of break force and fatigue life. By design, steel ropes used in permanent mooring systems will suffer negligible corrosion throughout their life. Corrosion will only tend to occur if the integrity of the rope structure is breached in other ways by e.g. cutting of the outer sheath.

4.2.3 Seabed contact and Particle Ingress

Seabed contact is not normally recommended for mooring ropes in operation as it may lead to wear or abrasion, particle ingress, or in the case of steel wire ropes, bending fatigue in the region of the touch down point. However, it is common for mooring ropes to be stored on the seabed prior to mooring system hook up and it can be acceptable for ropes to occasionally touch the seabed during operation (e.g. leeward lines in extreme weather).

The permeable nature of synthetic fibre ropes means that small particles (e.g. clay, silt or sand) can enter the rope and act as an abrasive medium. Ropes which are temporarily laid on the seabed or touch the seabed during operation are particularly at risk. Particles entering the load bearing core can accelerate wear in tension fatigue and can significantly influence the splice area [220].

4.2.4 Ultra-Violet (UV) Radiation and Marine Fouling

UV radiation is not normally considered a significant risk to mooring ropes in its own right (i.e. the risk of degradation to the mechanical properties of ropes is low). However, UV radiation accelerates marine growth which in turn can lead to other degradation mechanisms. To date, there has been relatively little research into marine growth on mooring ropes since chain is often the preferred material in the upper 100m of the mooring line with consequently minimal growth on mooring ropes.

For sheathed or jacketed rope types used in mooring, marine fouling is unlikely to penetrate into the load bearing parts of the rope and therefore not a direct threat to the strength or fatigue properties of mooring ropes. However, marine fouling can add significant weight to mooring lines and inhibit visual

examination. The added weight of marine growth on mooring ropes can alter their mechanical response and lead eventually to seabed contact which in turn poses a risk of abrasion and wear.

4.2.5 Tension Fatigue

In conventional mooring systems, fatigue life of ropes is normally greater than that of chain. Consequently, the chain in the system normally becomes the fatigue limiting component and little emphasis is placed on rope fatigue.

The main reason for their extended fatigue life is the high number of discrete components acting in parallel. For example, if local imperfections lead to premature failure of a single components in a rope (e.g. a filament or wire) the load at the failure locations can be re-distributed amongst the remaining components with negligible effect and the helical structure of ropes will enable the load to be transferred back into the damaged component either side of the failure location. In this way, damage can be isolated and will not propagate across the rope.

Classical models of fatigue tend to focus on stress range. However, for ropes the mean tension may also influence. Higher mean tension for the same stress range results in shorter fatigue life. For example, this characteristic is reflected in the fatigue slope of API 2SK [221] for steel ropes and the "TTR" (Time to Rupture") approach recommended by DNVGL for synthetic fibre ropes [222][223].

Published fatigue data for mooring ropes is based on the operating parameters and experience of oil and gas mooring systems. However, for many FWT mooring systems these assumptions may not be representative. For example, mean tensions may be lower, peak tensions may be higher, cycle frequency may be greater and without an ability to re-tension mooring lines the tension distribution between mooring lines may change over time.

4.2.6 Elongation and Axial Stiffness

All ropes will undergo some degree of permanent elongation when first loaded. For steel ropes this is not normally considered significant. However, for fibre ropes this elongation can influence mooring system integrity. For example, as a rope length increases the risk of seabed contact may increase, tensions may reduce and wear and fatigue modes (of both the rope and the system) may change. This characteristic may be particularly relevant in FWT mooring systems which, unlike oil and gas mooring systems, will have limited opportunity to re-tension lines. Due to both rope construction and material properties the axial stiffness of synthetic fibre ropes changes as a function of mean load, load range, cycle frequency and, most significantly, load history. Consequently, the axial stiffness properties cannot be taken as a constant and will evolve with the operation of the system.

4.3 Degradation, Damage Prevention and Mitigation

4.3.1 External Damage (Abrasion, Cutting and Wear)

Mitigation of external damage to ropes can be achieved by adding or increasing the robustness of external layers or by modifying operational practises to minimise the risk of damage occurring. It is important to note that abrasion, wear and cutting are not standardised parameter for ropes. Therefore, although they can be evaluated and even tested it can be difficult to systematically quantify both required performance and any enhancements.

Both synthetic fibre and steel mooring ropes are supplied with outer layers which protect from external damage. In both cases the effectiveness of these layers can be enhanced in two ways; by either increasing their thickness (e.g. ability to absorb damage) or increasing their robustness (e.g. using harder wearing materials or adding reinforcement to the layer). In the case of steel wire ropes, double thickness sheaths or sheaths from alternative polymers increasingly adopted whilst in synthetic fibre ropes materials increased or double thickness jackets are used along with materials such as HMPE or fine steel to enhance robustness.

Despite many years of experience in oil and gas operations, damage during installation, and, less frequently in operation, continues to be the principal degradation mechanisms of all sorts of mooring ropes. Considering the likely use of alternative installation vessels and install methods and the reduced redundancy in FWT mooring it is likely that additional robustness will be a key feature of FWT mooring ropes.

4.3.2 Corrosion

By nature of their shape and component structure it is possible to introduce a number of features that make corrosion in steel wire ropes almost negligible. For example, through the use of blocking compounds, wire coatings (e.g. galvanisation) and outer sheathing it can be assumed that corrosion is not a significant influencing factor in spiral strand rope life.

Table 9: Life expectancy for different types of steel ropes

Steel rope type	Life expectancy from [221]
Galvanized 6 – strand	6-8 years
Galvanized unjacketed spiral strand	10-12 years
Galvanized unjacketed spiral strand with zinc fillers	15-17 years
Galvanized jacketed spiral strand	20-25 years
Galvanized jacketed spiral strand with zinc fillers	30-35 years

This assumption relies not only on the use of these features, also on maintaining their integrity throughout the rope life. Consequently, whilst corrosion is not necessarily a primary consideration for steel wire ropes it can be a significant consequence of other forms of damage, particularly external damage where the plastic sheathing is breached.

4.3.3 Seabed contact and Particle Ingress

The wear and particle ingress associated with repeated seabed contact can be mitigated by the use of enhanced outer covers (e.g. sheaths or jackets) and (in the case of particle ingress) the use of filter systems [224]. Additionally, buoyancy elements can be used to prevent seabed contact during installation or in operation.

Although not common, some mooring systems are known to have been deployed with spiral strand operating (and hence bending) in the touch down zone. With suitable sheathing and armouring these systems have been shown to perform well in the long term. However, limited data is available to support the associated bending fatigue and so this operating mode may need to be evaluated in laboratory tests before it can be deployed as a standard design.

4.3.4 Ultra-Violet (UV) Radiation and Marine Fouling

Marine fouling may be mitigated directly (i.e. by preventing or limiting its growth) or by mitigating its consequences (i.e. either enabling regular seabed contact or by counter acting the weight of marine growth). Whilst buoyancy systems exist for ropes the experience of the MODU sector is that the connections of these systems to ropes are often not reliable and can easily fail. Consequently, alternative mitigations are likely to be required for FWT mooring ropes in shallow water.

4.3.5 Tension Fatigue

Tension fatigue effects are mitigated in both steel and fibre ropes through design and material choices. Both steel and synthetic fibre ropes make use of lubricants to minimise the impact of the interaction between components. In the case of synthetic fibre ropes the effectiveness of these lubricants is tested as a standard quality control test [225]. Additionally, rope designs for mooring

make use of lower lay angles than typical for other rope types (e.g. running ropes) which further enhances their tension fatigue endurance [226].

Neither synthetic fibre parallel sub-rope or steel wire spiral strand constructions are designed to be suitable for regular bending. However, spiral strand ropes can suffer from unrestrained bending at the interface of the rope and the termination (socket). This phenomena is normally limited through the use of bend limiters which ensure any bending movement of the rope is transferred to the socket.

It should also be noted that synthetic fibre ropes with low axial stiffness (such as nylon) are highly effective in reducing peak loads and consequently reducing the fatigue loads in a system [227].

4.3.6 Elongation and Axial Stiffness

The change in length properties of synthetic fibre ropes is an ongoing challenge for mooring system designers. A number of modelling and testing protocols have been developed to manage and quantify this characteristic [228][229]. Whilst these same protocols may be usefully applied to FWT mooring it will be imperative to build new data sets based on the application specific rope designs, materials and load cases.

4.4 Summary

Synthetic fibre ropes are used in mooring systems when reduced weight and/or compliance of low axial stiffness materials are required. Polyester has traditionally been the preferred material for oil and gas deep water mooring systems, due to its axial stiffness, strength and fatigue characteristics. However, in recent years polyester mooring systems have been developed for increasingly shallow water applications.

On the other hand, steel wire ropes have high axial stiffness, high strength and medium weight, are used in mooring systems where their weight or robustness is an advantage, and the weight of a full chain system is impractical.

As any other mooring system solution ropes are subjected to a number of degradation mechanisms such as external damage, corrosion (in wire ropes), UV radiation and marine fouling, seabed contact and particle ingress, tension fatigue and elongation and axial stiffness (in synthetic ropes).

The special characteristics of ropes (i.e. weight, stiffness and fatigue performance) and the impact of the associated degradation mechanisms affects design and operation of mooring systems- While many issues and concerns have been solved for the oil and gas industry, other new issues have arisen from the special requirements of FOW.

5. Inspection Methods and Tools

5.1 Introduction

Inspection and monitoring of mooring lines are common practice used to ensure the continued integrity of mooring assets; they provide the required data to assess fitness-for purpose of the mooring system. Due to the nature of mooring systems' operational environment, mooring lines are subjected to several damage mechanisms as described in sections 3.2 and 0. Furthermore, the operating environment has led to mooring lines to be designed with considerable redundancy and a significant factor of safety (FoS), regardless of this fact, failure is not uncommon in the existing mooring systems.

For O&G floating structures, periodic in-service inspections of mooring systems are generally performed as part of the integrity management programme. Detail of inspection type and frequencies are provided in section 5.4.

Mooring lines inspection are generally costly; offshore inspection requires support vessels, crew and equipment with substantial daily rate. More indication on costs are given in section 5.5.

The challenge with FOWT and similarly with long term FPSs is that as they are required to remain in a fixed position for a significant period, dry-docking inspection is not a viable option as is discussed in API RP 2I: In-service Inspection of Mooring Hardware for Floating Structures [19]. Therefore, there remains a significance dependence on diver, ROV and where required NDT inspections and assessments.

5.2 Inspection Practices

The offshore industry has come to rely on regular in-service inspections of mooring systems as part of the integrity management program. During the asset lifetime, this program generally includes three types of inspections:

- Baseline Inspections
- In-Service Inspection
- Ad-Hoc inspections

5.2.1 Baseline Inspection

For a newly installed facility, before the commencement of the regular operations and integrity management strategy, a baseline inspection should be undertaken. The purpose of the baseline inspection is to identify any damage during installation. This inspection behaves as the baseline for comparison for all inspections scheduled through the service life whilst also serving as the reference point as from which the fitness for service can be determined; therefore, inspection can be conducted thoroughly with ample detail. Baseline inspections of mooring system generally include only a visual inspection unless damage is known, and detailed examination is required. They should be conducted within 3 months after the initial hook-up [20].

5.2.2 Periodic In-Service Inspection

A periodic inspection is performed as part of the plan to ensure relevant information is collected to evaluate the ongoing fitness for service.

Periodic inspections are typically scheduled based around the age, condition and operational history of the mooring line, or based on a quantification of the risk of failure. Frequency of periodic inspections is vital in ensuring predictable and safe operations. Variable factors play a role in dictating when an inspection event should take place. The integrity management strategy in place is typically the biggest driver. environment, weather events, type of mooring line, prior inspection results, age of mooring system, availability of vessels and personnel also affect the time between inspection. Inspection planning and frequencies are discussed in more detail in section 5.2.4.

With regards to planning, inspection windows may be dictated by benign weather condition, where vessel downtime due to adverse weather is expected to have less impact or during periods where vessel daily rates are low, and appropriate personnel are available. Such considerations will benefit OPEX and operational efficiency.

5.2.3 Ad-Hoc Inspection

Major weather event, unpredicted structural failure or impact with a vessel could warrant a special event inspection. These are unplanned and are done due to fears of significant damage. Other opportunities for ad-hoc inspection can arise during the life through other field intervention or activity and are therefore considered to optimise vessel time and to inspect specific areas of interest.

5.2.4 Inspection Schedule

There are great variances with the frequency of mooring inspections between operators on the O&G. Inspection schedule may be mandated in order to comply with legislative requirements which may be different around the world; on the other hand, International Standards generally give recommendation on inspection frequency rather than mandatory requirement. This result in great variances as operator try to minimise inspection to reduce operating costs.

International Standards do not mandate a specific inspection interval, however API RP 2I [20] recommend a maximum interval between major inspection which depend on how many years the line has been in service. These have been reported in Table 10 for chain and wire ropes.

While legislative requirements differ around the world, during the operational phase of any asset, the intent is to operate the equipment within its design limits and to minimise the risk of failure to a level as low as reasonably practicable (ALARP). Within the oil and gas sectors a risk-based approach is typically used and widely accepted. This approach is better described in Section 5.3.1

Table 10: Chain and Wire Rope inspection intervals [20]

	Years in service	Maximum Interval between Inspection
Chain	0 - 3	36 Months
	4 - 10	24 Months
	Over 10	8 Months
Wire Rope	0 - 2	18 Months
	3 - 5	12 Months
	Over 5	9 Months

5.3 Mooring Integrity Management Practices

Mooring integrity management (MIM) is a continuous practice that involves the managing of effects detrimental to the operation of the asset and prevents against accidents as well as minimising downtime and reducing economic loss. This process is constantly evolving according to the health of the mooring lines which can be determined through monitoring and inspection which forms the part of the Integrity Management (IM) process and is critical in determining the FFS of the mooring system from installation through to decommissioning.

5.3.1 Current Status

Currently, mooring integrity management strategies employed by the O&G industries revolve around API RP 2MIM which details the steps and requirements for an IM process, see Figure 42 below. The process revolving around a potential IM for the FOW will be virtually identical.

Figure 42: IM Process [21]

5.3.1.1 Data

Data is said to fall under one of two categories: characteristic data and condition data.

Characteristic data revolves around general mooring data, mooring design data, mooring fabrication data and mooring installation data and the baseline inspection data. This is the baseline data which represents the mooring at installation. It is crucial that this set of information is stored and accessible to provide a foundation to assess the current state of integrity.

Condition data represents any changes that may have occurred to the characteristics data throughout the working life of the mooring system. This should include all inspection data, damage evaluation data, corrosion protection data, any modifications and operational incidents. Condition data should be

updated regularly to give early indication to any changes in the systems condition. This can be aided with the inclusion of a digital twin (DT) into the IM strategy. Real-time data can be used to simulate the current condition of the mooring system which can then be used to perform an FFS evaluation.

5.3.1.2 Data Management

All the data acquired throughout the life of the mooring system should be collated in the data management system (DMS). It is the duty of the owner/operator to retain the records relating to integrity management.

5.3.1.3 Evaluation

The purpose of the evaluation phase of the IM strategy is to evaluate the FFS of the mooring system using the data and through forms of inspection and testing. In order to do this, the IM strategy must identify and take into consideration any threats, consequences of failure and also the risk profile of the mooring system. As the risk profile can change due to degradation and damage mechanisms the process of evaluation continues throughout the life of the mooring system. Through the evaluation process can result in no further action being required or the need to perform further assessment which may lead to remediation, modification of operating procedures, additional monitoring, and additional or more frequent inspection.

5.3.1.4 Risk-Based Inspection Approach

A Risk-Based Inspection (RBI) Approach involves developing an inspection scheme based on risk.

The methodology utilises qualitative or quantitative assessment of the probability of failure (PoF) and the consequence of failure (CoF) associated with a failure mechanism and the risk is defined as the product between PoF and CoF.

RBI is typically used to identify and understand the risk drivers to prioritize other inspection and integrity management activities. It can also be used to define desktop activities (analysis) that can reduce the uncertainties around the true damage state of the equipment and the circumstances that may lead to damage occurring.

International engineering standards and practices that relate to RBI include:

- API RP 580: Risk Based Inspection – an example of the minimum guidelines for implementation of an effective, credible RBI program
- API RP 581: Risk Based Inspection Base Resource Document – an example of an RBI methodology's technical basis

API RP580/581 was developed specifically for process equipment (piping circuits and vessels) and not for subsea systems and mooring lines, however the principle of the methodologies can be applied to any type of asset.

This approach, if correctly applied to mooring lines, it is capable of recognising which components within a mooring system are at a greater risk and can warrant a more detailed and more frequent inspection than mooring systems at a lower risk.

Aside from the highlighting the needs for an inspection, an RBI is also able to detail the risks from a safety/health/environment perspective and/or from an economic standpoint. From this an optimised approach to inspection planning can be taken.

The completion of a risk matrix assists in targeting inspection to critical areas that require attention, the categorised mooring risk can be used to establish inspection intervals as part of the greater risk-based approach. Both qualitative and quantitative methods are acceptable for the development of an RBI plan. Factors that can affect the outcome of an RBI are the complexity of the mooring system in question and the quality of the available data. For a qualitative risk assessment of mooring systems, the main objective is to classify the mooring components that have high failure rates, those whose

failure have great consequences and to increase or decrease the inspection scope for components as the approach sees fit.

Consequence of Failure	High	Risk Level 2	Risk Level 1	Risk Level 1
	Medium	Risk Level 3	Risk Level 2	Risk Level 1
	Low	Risk Level 3	Risk Level 3	Risk Level 2
		Low	Medium	High
		Likelihood of Failure		

Figure 43: RBI Matrix [21]

5.3.1.5 Strategy

The IM strategy represents the overall inspection and mitigation philosophies for the mooring system. The mooring probability of failure developed as part of the evaluation is used as part of inspection planning and risk reduction options.

A fundamental aspect of the IM strategy is the inspection plan which details the scope, tool, techniques and the deployment method of the inspection. An inspection plan should be developed for each mooring system and should cover the predicted service life. During any form of evaluation, the plan should be updated.

5.3.1.6 Program - process

The program phase of the IM process is concerned with the execution of the detailed work scope and should be conducted to complete methodologies defined in the strategy.

5.3.2 Improvements required

One of the challenges that the FOW industry has to face is related to operational costs, given the smaller margins compared to the O&G industry. In order to tackle this, the IM strategy can make use of technologies such as a digital twin to aid in creating an optimised strategy where all factors which typically result in high expenditure can be streamlined. For example, during an inspection survey the O&G industry typically perform an inspection on all lines however with a digital twin, inspection efforts can be targeted precisely where required.

To keep OPEX at a minimum, it is conceivable that an optimisation of design, suitable inspection and integrity management strategy and adequate sensor data through the use of a digital twin that only the essential number of mooring lines are inspected and maintained at the most efficient time.

With regards to monitoring systems and related technologies, enabling line failure detection and alarm systems (i.e. through the implementation of SHM) would be beneficial given that the system can be made accurate and reliable in offshore conditions. The monitoring system can aid in building a case for life extension for the asset or adjusting the inspection schedule and/or scope. The monitoring

should allow for the identification of irregular behaviour given the operating conditions, warnings upon possible damage, preventing against faults of greater scope and cost. However, it must be taken into account that such monitoring system should be calibrated/tuned to each mooring system, which tends to be unique.

5.4 Current Inspection Methods and Technologies

5.4.1 Methods

There are several approaches to mooring system inspection, they vary in effectiveness, cost and suitability. The most popular inspection method is visual, this is due to its relative simplicity and comparatively low costs. Line inspection conventionally consists of the cleaning, inspection and measurement. The purpose of an inspection is to obtain adequate visual records through, pictures and videos, and measurements to define any potential anomaly that is found.

5.4.1.1 Visual

Typical methods for performing visual inspection are diver and ROV, both mentioned inspection methods are performed in-situ [21]. API RP 2MIM, a RP dedicated to mooring integrity management, details that there are three levels of visual inspection, they are defined as general, close and detailed visual inspections (GVI, CVI and DVI). GVI does not require the cleaning of marine growth where CVI and DVI does. Hence a GVI is completed to identify any gross anomalies and damage. This criterion is met during the fly-by inspection during the beginning of an inspection campaign. From this point, the decision to proceed with a CVI on the areas that require will it made, in addition to this, previous inspection anomaly data will also require updating through close or detailed inspections. CVI as well as DVI requires the removal of marine growth, this is typically performed by hand wire brushes (diver) or high-pressure water jetting (ROV). This is often back to bare metal. And increase in corrosion can be expected due to exposing bare metal or damaging the protective coatings. The purpose of this is to obtain clear visual of the line's surface to allow for further classify and understand the abnormality. Typical damage methods found during CVI are corrosion, pitting, cracking, or weld damage. DVI is used to perform and examination on the condition of specific components to detect and record localised damage, deterioration, defects, debris and other anomalies. Based on the finding's further inspection, such as various NDT methods can be performed if required. With the information gathered, the likely length of time the component can safely remain operational can be determined, repair procedures can be conducted, or the component can be taken out of service and a replacement installed.

Given that there are multiple types/materials for mooring lines, there are several different damage mechanisms that can be apparent for each. Chains, usually made of a carbon steel, are prone to pitting corrosion, fatigue cracks, wear and corrosion at the flash butt weld on the chain links (see chapter 3). Areas of observed deformation or deterioration should be quantified and recorded. Wire rope inspection should focus on damage to PE sheathing, any exposed metal, changes in diameter which would indicate elongation, twisting, kinking, bird-caging or broken wires. Focus should also be given to termination points. Similar damage mechanisms are apparent for fibre ropes however they include abrasion and wear (see chapter 0).

It is not uncommon for mobile offshore units to perform visual inspections during mooring retrieval upon completion of a project, although the effectiveness of these inspections is questioned. For permanent or long-term moorings, like those to found in the floating wind industry, where the facility to retract mooring lines is not present, this type of visual inspection is not possible.

API RP2I - utilises both diver and ROV for MODU mooring inspection. Diver for shallow and ROV for deep-water.

5.4.1.1.1 Diver

Mooring system inspection via diver has been a popular and successful method for assessing asset conditions subsea in the O&G industry. There are apparent limitations with the depths a human can dive. The depths displayed below in Table 11 indicate that divers are not best suited for the inspection of the thrash zone, an area prone to high amounts of wear and a common failure point for mooring lines. The risk of diving to great depth poses some health risks such as nitrogen narcosis [22].

Table 11: Diving Depths

Diving Method	Diving Depth (m)
Surface air supply	60
Oxygen Helium mixture	90
Bell Bounce diver	180
Saturation Diver	600

Divers are best suited for inspections in the splash zone as it is close to the surface. This typically covers components including the top chain and connector. This area is prone to greater marine growth as well as pitting corrosion. Removal of marine growth through hand wire brushes is common, care is to be taken to not damage protective coatings. Furthermore, smaller diving depths require less diving equipment.

The versatility of a diver-based inspection allows for a mooring line to be a chain, synthetic rope or a wire rope. With the appropriate training a diver will be able to perform the necessary procedures. The task of inspecting mooring lines via diver is a hazardous one. As mooring line are dynamic in their function of station keeping, they are capable of moving during an inspection and could potentially cause serious harm to the diver. Therefore, much apprehension remains about sending individuals into that environment. Safety for obvious reasons is of the utmost priority during all activities. Adding to the risk is the fact that many of the measuring devices and cameras are cumbersome, adding to fatigue and hindering manoeuvrability. API RP 21 highlights this risk stating that an inspection should be modified to ensure minimal risk to inspection personnel whilst ensuring the inspection objectives are not compromised. In addition to this, the HSE's JIP of FPS mooring integrity [23], compiled by the HSE UK, diver-based inspection is known to yield inconsistent results as the level of experience and ability of each diver differs.

Poor weather and lighting conditions prevents divers from entering the water due to the risk posed to the safety of the divers. Poor visibility with heavy rain can delay any inspection which drives up the associated costs.

With the FOW industry in mind, the depths for FOWT turbines will likely dictate which inspection method or a combination of them both is best suited to perform inspection duties.

5.4.1.1.2 Remotely Operated Vehicle

Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs) often perform in-situ visual inspections through the use of cameras providing a live feed of subsea assets such as mooring line, allowing them to assess the current state of the line. In addition to this, a recording is also taken for future reference and archiving. During an inspection campaign, ROVs are capable of detecting many types of damage mechanisms through visual means. Suitable for inspecting any type of mooring line design and material.

Tethered to the inspection support vessel, ROVs are remotely controlled via a joystick. The nature of ROVs allows for the pilot and engineers to be in a controlled environment on the vessel, this significantly reduces any potential risks associated to personnel during inspection. With safety of

personnel being of the utmost priority, this gives this visual inspection an edge over diver-based inspections.

Various types of ROV are available to perform various tasks. With some purely for recreational use and others for cable burial. Given that versatility can be added, rotating wire/nylon brushes or high-pressure water jets capable of removing marine growth are optional tools. It is possible for some ROVs to perform NDT measuring and NDT activities through the installation of appropriate sensors. For these activities it is recommended that a class III ROV is used, see Figure 44 - Working Class ROV [24]. Table 12 below lists the capability and class of available ROV for commercial use.

Table 12: ROV Classification

ROV Class	Capability
Class I	Pure observation
Class II	Observation with payload option
Class III	Working-Class
Class IV	Towed and bottom-crawling vehicles
Class V	Prototype or development vehicles

Figure 44 - Working Class ROV [24]

It is possible for a ROV to damage a mooring line through contact. In the case the ROV pilot is inexperienced and does not know the limitations of the vehicle. This is generally considered during the risk assessment process prior to commencing inspection. An inspection campaign can also be severely hindered by operational team's knowledge relating to mooring integrity and damage mechanisms. Furthermore, ensuring the quality and lighting is of adequate quality to allow for thorough assessment is vital along with guaranteeing sufficient time to perform a survey. Additionally, poor environmental conditions such as high wind speeds, heavy rain and strong currents can make the operational conditions for the support crew hazardous, as well make manoeuvrability and visibility difficult, preventing ROVs from entering the water.

Table 13 Factors affecting ROV inspection.

Table 13: Factors affecting ROV inspection [25]Hardware	Operational	Human
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suitability of ROV for specific survey • Types of lights and cameras fitted to the ROV • Dimensions of ROV and any tooling compared to the size of the access to the inspection site. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocated survey time • General visibility • Marine growth elapsed time since significant weather • Width of any mooring line trench in relation to the size of the ROV 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depth of knowledge of mooring system integrity issues of person specifying survey and preparing survey pack • Depth of knowledge of ROVs operational team of mooring system integrity issues. Both in terms of what to look for and the views that will be of the greatest value to those reviewing the footage.

5.4.2 Non-Destructive Testing

Non-destructive testing (NDT) is a method of identifying and understanding damage mechanisms to a higher degree of accuracy and detail than visual inspections. This form of material testing is done without affecting in any way the operational ability of a part or material, this adds to the usefulness NDT. Many of the NDT methods can be used with the aid of a diver or an ROV. In-situ inspection of mooring lines through means of NDT poses added complexity over on-shore inspections. In order to successfully complete an NDT survey, thorough knowledge on the application, including setting up and calibration of the test equipment is required by either the diver or the ROV pilot and support crew.

5.4.2.1 Magnetic Particle Inspection

Magnetic particle inspection (MPI) is a method used to detect surface and near surface cracks in ferromagnetic materials and is commonly used in the manufacturing and installations processes. It is common practice with MPI to inspect the flash butt weld of every link and 10% of all accessible surfaces of links. One of the key limitations of MPI is that rough surfaces of the majority of chain links may create false positives. MPI is an NDT method feasible to be used underwater however given the context of mooring line inspection, the geometry may limit what areas of the chain can be inspected.

5.4.2.2 Ultrasonic Testing

Ultrasonic testing (UT) is a technique used to determine both surface and subsurface defects. UT makes use of sound waves ranging from 500KHz to 20MHz which are passed through a material and bounce back, ultrasonic based inspections are typically used to detect flaws, perform dimensional measurements and material characterisation. UT is typically used for the inspection of the region around flash butt welds, an area where subsurface defects are often prevalent. Both divers and ROVs are capable of performing UT providing appropriate training and hardware is undertaken/available.

5.4.2.3 Acoustic Emission Testing

Acoustic emission testing (AET) utilises sensors designed to detect the elastic energy waves naturally released when undergoing deformation. The waves can be produced from several forms including cavitation, friction and impact. Small plastic changes at any point within a material are capable of producing significant waves, aiding in the detection, locating and characterising the defect. It is an effective method for the inspection of welds due to stress concentrations forming due to the hot work

required during manufacturing. The greatest difficulty with utilising AET is that a loud working environment can hamper the accuracy of the test.

5.4.2.4 Magnetic Flux Leakage

Magnetic flux leakage (MFL) can be used to assess the condition of both unsheathed wire rope by saturating the wire rope to maximum flux density using a powerful magnet. Where a defect or a breakage in the wire rope is present the magnetic flux leaks out from the rope, indicating the location of the damage. It is effective for the detection of forms of corrosion and breakages in the rope. Where MPI is limited to the detection of surface and near surface defects, MFL can detect defects deep within a material.

5.4.3 State of the art technologies

5.4.3.1 Chain Measurement System

Figure 45 – Chain Measurement System [26]

An optical measuring technology developed by Welaptega, displayed in Figure 45 – Chain Measurement System [26], utilises the digital image produced by several cameras to feed a specialised software located on the vessel. From the detailed image, accurate, repeatable, and reliable chain measurements can be obtained. CMS claims to be capable of quantitatively measuring the diameter of the grip zone (chain crown) in both locations, the length of each link and the mooring line angle. Measuring the chain dimensions is important with regards to wear rate and ensuring minimum strength. An accuracy of less than +/- 1mm is claimed. CMS requires the use of a ROV to slide the tool up or down the chain and has an operational depth of up to 3000m.

5.4.3.2 Rope Measurement System

Figure 46 - Rope Measurement System [27]

The rope measurement system (RMS), depicted in Figure 46, is a technology to identify variations in the cross-section of or both wire and synthetic fibre ropes. It consists of four high resolution cameras which record the rope's cross section whilst being towed by an ROV along the mooring line either in-situ or removed. Footage is transmitted in real time to a data-logger located on the support vessel. Algorithms are used to process measurements of the rope at approximately 50mm intervals in order to build a profile of the rope to display any anomalous findings. In addition to cross-section, the length of the rope is measured to establish the creep model. In the case where marine growth is prevalent, rollers and brushes are used to clear it.

5.4.3.3 Semi-Autonomous Mooring Inspection Robot

Figure 47 - SAMIR [28]

The Semi-Autonomous Mooring Inspection Robot (SAMIR), displayed in Figure 47, is a technology developed primarily to perform the inspection of wire rope. SAMIR is designed to be used in conjunction with a ROV in order to perform its crawling duties up and down the mooring line. The machine is capable of performing NDT in the form of MFL giving it the ability to determine if broken or corroded wires are present on both sheathed and unsheathed wire rope.

5.5 Inspection Costs

Offshore operations are generally very costly and require specialised personnel and equipment.

Generally, to perform a subsea visual inspection of mooring lines the following is required:

- ROV support vessel (and related vessel crew in shifts)
- Inspection class ROV fitted with camera and video
- ROV crew (2-3 persons for 12hr shift)

If a more detailed inspection is required, the ROV may be fitted with additional instrument (i.e. UT probes etc.) at additional costs. This would usually be the case for inspecting a mooring line.

Inspections are generally charged at a day rate which is generally different whether the vessel/equipment is in stand-by or in operation. Weather conditions may affect the inspection productivity therefore it is important that inspections are scheduled when weather conditions are expected to be benign, typically during the summer months.

Vessel cost depends on many factors, including the inspection location, vessel size and contract duration. The longer the contract the cheaper are the rates that operators are able to negotiate. Because of the extensive amount of offshore operations that are generally required to operate either

an O&G field or an offshore wind farm, operators may hire support vessel for general maintenance on yearly contracts and are therefore able to take advantage of significant lower rates. Sharing the costs with other operators in the vicinity is also an option if both parties can align their inspection dates. Finally, during industry downturns, especially within the oil and gas industry, lower rates are also easier to negotiate.

The duration of the inspection also depends on the type of inspection required, other than being influenced by weather condition. For a simple GVI where the ROV can quickly scan the mooring line in search of evident sign of damage giving an overview of the condition, the duration is generally reduced. However, for detailed CVI inspections and NDT activities the duration is much longer. In addition, the majority of the times the mooring lines may require cleaning from marine growth before the inspection is performed, this may also add additional time to the total length of the operation.

For the reasons above it is difficult to estimate cost of inspection, however average day rates are given based on industry experience:

Table 14: Visual Inspection Costs

	Average day rates [€/day]
Support Vessel	10,000 – 30,000
Inspection class ROV	3,000-5,000
ROV crew (*)	1,000
Other inspection equipment (**)	1,000-10,000

(*) cost per person. Generally 4-6 people required for 24hr operation

(**) depends on the type of inspection

Considering, for example the average of the prices in Table 12, for 7-day operation for a visual inspection we have a total daily cost of 30,000EUR and a total cost for 7 days of 210,000 EUR

5.6 Review of Codes/Standard - Gap Analysis between O&G and FOW

The main codes and standards which provide requirement and recommendations on mooring system inspection and integrity management that are available in the industry are:

- API RP 2I In Service Inspection of Mooring Hardware for Floating Structures
- API RP 2MIM Mooring Integrity Management
- ISO/DIS 19901-7 Station keeping system for floating offshore structures and mobile offshore units

The key requirements regarding mooring inspection have been reported in the following sections.

Due to the obvious similarities between station keeping philosophies, namely, mooring lines in MODUs, FPSOs and other similar floating structures, the analysis of the following codes provide useful guidance on the mooring integrity issues faced by the O&G industry and outlines what the FOW industry should do in order to not face the same issues as O&G.

With regards to inspection strategies and OPEX, with the total number of mooring lines comfortable sitting above three figures, it is not feasible to inspect all lines thoroughly beyond the baseline inspection. Therefore, a methodology utilising data from monitoring sources will have to be implemented to keep OPEX at an acceptable level, adding to the LCOE.

5.6.1 API RP 2I - 3rd edition, 2008

5.6.1.1 Inspection

API RP 2I aims to fill the requirements for a guide to effective inspection of mooring hardware of floating structures. This is done through detailing in-service inspection both dockside and offshore, of catenary and taut mooring systems with the coinciding jewellery, all for floating structures. It should be emphasised that although this RP caters for floating structures, significant preference is given to MODUs since the document was initially written for the in-air inspection of mooring components for MODUs only. In this latest version, the scope had been expanded to include other floating structures and underwater inspection. This recommended practice places responsibility of implementation or adaption in the best judgement of the engineers, given a difference in application.

According to API RP 2I this is done by outlining the requirements for effective planning of a mooring inspection, performing a mooring inspection, concluding the action after analysing the inspection results and communicating the concerns about mooring hardware.

5.6.1.2 For Chain

- Inspection to confirm wear and corrosion is within the design limits
- Determine the integrity of connectors
- Types of inspection: as-built survey, periodic surveys, ad-hoc inspections (see section 5.1.1)
- Factors leading to inspection include: age, condition, operational history type of mooring, area and nature of operation, seafloor condition, water depth and class requirements.
- Prior to an inspection, the following information should be collated and provided to the inspector: Chain type (stud-less or stud-link), grade, diameter (nominal and bar) and other link dimensions, segment length, MBS, manufacturer and year made.
- Particular care should be taken in the inspection of the fairlead region; splash zone; touch-down region; connectors.

5.6.1.3 For Wire rope

- Prior to an inspection, the following information should be collated and provided to the inspector: Wire rope. Construction (six-strand or spiral strand), jacket (sheathed or unsheathed), corrosion protection (galvanized wires, zinc filler wires, anodes on socket, blocking compound), termination (socket type, tri-plate, etc.), diameter (bare, with jacket), segment length, MBS, manufacturer and year made, re-tension hardware.
- Areas to focus inspection: Broken wires, corrosion, sheath damage and sockets.
- Bird caging or kinking, broken wires, missing anodes on socket or wore rope included in the discard criteria.

5.6.1.4 For Fibre rope

- For fibre ropes, an inspection strategy should be developed by mooring system operator, mooring manufacturer and in conjunction with the appropriate certifying authority.
- Prior to an inspection, the following information should be collated and provided to the inspector: rope construction (number of sub-ropes in rope and number of strands in sub-rope), jacket (type, material), filter type and filtering capability, splicing method (individual or paired, etc.), diameter, segment length, MBS, manufacturer and year made.
- The ability of GVI to identify damage to the exterior of the fibre rope depends upon underwater visibility and extent of marine growth.
- Any form of damage that corresponds to maximum break strength reduction of 10% is reason to take the rope out of service.

The inspection objectives, types, and schedule established for chain and wire rope can generally be applied to fibre rope.

The following should be recorded on the inspection record regardless for the type of mooring line:

- Operation history, including inspection and failure history and previous operating locations
- Type of inspection (as-built, periodic, or special survey) and inspection method (diver or ROV)
- Locations and nature of all component abnormalities, and corrective measures taken
- Recommendations for further action to be taken.

5.6.1.5 Limitations

Significant focus in this standard is given to on in-air inspection for MODU, with limited guidance on underwater inspection of mooring lines by means of either diver or ROV.

5.6.2 API RP 2MIM - 1st edition, 2019

API RP 2MIM provides guidance for the MIM for FPSs as a way to ensure the FFS of the asset for the entirety of the asset's design life. The RP is intended for the application of permanently moored FS which includes spread, catenary anchor leg and taut leg mooring systems, notably tension leg mooring is not supported by this document. With regards to FOW this is not much of a hindrance.

Understanding condition and the threats to the integrity of assets is a crucial aspect of creating and successfully implementing a MIM programme, inspection through visual and other means plays an irreplaceable role in the MIM.

5.6.2.1 Inspection

API RP 2MIM gives a comprehensive overview of planning and procedure of performing a general, close or detailed visual inspection. Considering the mooring integrity management, the inspection and strategy are described to be crucial. The aspects that are to be defined within an inspection plan are: frequency, scope of inspection, tools and techniques to be used, and the method of deployment. The inspection plan should be developed for the mooring and should cover the anticipated remaining service life. The plan should be periodically updated throughout the mooring's service life following receipt and evaluation of IM data, e.g. inspection data, results of mooring assessments, etc. The following basic elements should be included in the inspection plan: baseline, periodic and ad-hoc inspections (further details provided in section 5.2.1).

Each of the forms of inspection should identify any possible failure modes associated with the mooring type. From the inspection the knowledge gained should be used to make an informed decision on the likely for the degradation form to become critical, this will form part of the strategy.

Results of inspection and monitoring activities should be evaluated against the design envelope to determine if there are changes outside of the envelope. If changes are outside the envelope, then assessment initiators should be triggered.

5.6.2.2 Maintenance

Maintenance is conducted in accordance with the result of monitoring data and inspection results.

Aside from the implementation of a risk-based approach, details on how maintenance should be conducted is not provided in RP 2MIM.

5.6.3 ISO/DIS 19901-7 - 01/2018

ISO 19901-7 is part seven of a greater series of specific requirements for offshore floating structures. This specific document focuses on station keeping systems for floating offshore structures and mobile offshore units. The design, analysis and evaluation of mooring systems are considered and is applicable to all aspects of the life-cycle, including the manufacture in-service inspections. ISO 19901-7 covers a wide range of mooring types including; catenary, taut-line and semi-taut-line, single point

and dynamic positioning. Some of which can be directly related to the floating structures proposed in the FOW industry.

Limited guidance is offered with regards inspection techniques and methods to be implemented; responsibility is given to owner/operator to ensure appropriate arrangements are made to ensure the integrity of the mooring system. This typically involves inspections and where required planned maintenance. Methods, frequency and scope of inspection events are to be sufficient as to provide assurance that the mooring systems integrity is within the design envelope. Fatigue assessments are to be completed for all permanent mooring components to CVI or NDT level within a timeframe defined by a recognised classification society.

5.7 Summary

A wide range of inspection technologies exist with varying levels of detail ranging from general visual inspection to focused NDT tools designed mooring lines.

Presently, there is a clear need for tailored documentation focusing on the unique challenges facing FOW industry with respects to mooring systems inspection and integrity management.

API 2MIM comes close to what is required for the IM of potential FOW mooring systems. However, having a specific risk-based method tailored to apply to the FOW industry will enhance the effective operation of the floating structure whilst reducing any excessive activities to reduce costs.

6. Failure Detection by SHM

6.1 Introduction

According to [213], a fault (error) is an “unpermitted deviation of at least one characteristic property (feature) of the system from the acceptable, usual or standard condition”. There exist many types of faults, for example design, manufacturing, operation (e.g. wear), internal or external. A fault is independent of whether the system is in operation or not and it may not affect the correct functioning of the system. Faults affect internal process parameters (stiffness, resistance...) or internal state variables (temperature, movement, etc.) which are frequently difficult to detect, especially if they are small or hidden, and measure. The control of the system may hide the effects of the faults. Faults may develop stepwise or drift wise, slowly or fast.

Going back to [213], a failure is a “permanent interruption of a system’s ability to perform a required function under specified operating conditions” whilst the malfunction is “an intermittent irregularity in the fulfilment of a system’s desired function”. A fault can be seen as a state and the failure and malfunction as an event. Damage, depending on the field, is used as equivalent to fault or to failure.

Failures and malfunction result from one or more faults. Usually a failure arises after begin of operation or by increasingly stressing the system. During the lifetime of the system, the typical failure rate is described by the so called “bathtub- curve”, where the rate is bigger during infant period (burn in, exponential decrease) and the ageing period (wear out, exponential increase). The useful life is the period between those initial and final periods, where the failure rate keeps constant.

Supervision aims to show the current state and indicate faulty states (monitoring) and taking appropriate counteractions to avoid malfunctions or failures, and of course, accidents (protection). The deviations from normal process behaviour result from faults and errors may result in some shorter or longer periods with malfunctions or failures if no counteractions are taken.

In order to avoid malfunctions or failures, continuous condition monitoring is essential in a risk-based integrity strategy in order to balance the risk and the costly inspection and maintenance operations.

6.2 SHM

Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) aims at extracting fault-sensitive features from the measured signals and using them to analyze the system’s condition. Thereby, SHM provides information regarding the system’s state of health, performance and usage, e.g. loading conditions. SHM may be considered as a four-step process [30]: (i) operational evaluation, (ii) data-acquisition, (iii) feature extraction, and (iv) diagnosis. Operational evaluation refers to a preliminary step where the system’s criticality, providing an economic/safety justification of the SHM system, based on indicators such as business impact, direct costs, machine’s integrity, or safety risks. After this evaluation, SHM begins by measuring the system response, using signals such as acceleration, acoustic signals, and electric variables.

After this data-acquisition step, the available measurements are used to extract features that represent the system’s condition. Changes in these features indicate changes in the system’s properties, which may be related to faults, early degradation or malfunctioning. Detecting such changes inherently implies a comparison between a healthy state, a faulty state and its different levels in between. To that end, a model of the system is required, which will represent the behaviour of the system and act as a baseline for the comparison. In a data-driven approach, such a model is obtained in a training phase, where the system’s output history is used to determine the system’s behaviour under different operational conditions and fault scenarios. This comparison between the baseline model and the current state is carried out in a final step, which aims at evaluating the extracted features, to classify

and quantify the underlying cause for a change in the system. Common solutions to the classification of these features are the derivation of statistical models using machine learning techniques [30], or the heuristic indicators based on domain expert experience [31].

Depending on the monitoring method and the available data, four diagnosis levels may be achieved [32]: (i) fault detection (true/false), (ii) fault localization (where), (iii) fault identification (extent), and (iv) prognosis (remaining useful life). In general, fault detection could be achieved using a baseline model which considers solely the system's healthy state. However, if the SHM system aims at identifying the underlying fault among different possible fault scenarios, the current state will have to be compared with all the potential fault scenarios. In other words, the system's baseline model (and training phase) will need to account for all potential fault scenarios and operational conditions.

SHM systems are a crucial resource to reduce inspection costs and breakdown chances of mooring lines. Mooring lines are critical components which significantly affect the FOWT's stability, and whose failure may lead to significant costs and delays. Based on historical records of the Oil and Gas sector, such failures happen even though high safety-factors and first-class inspection methods are used [33][34]. Considering that FOW farms require a significantly larger number of mooring lines, this system's integrity is even more critical than in the Oil and Gas sector. Therefore, FOW industry will require more efficient monitoring solutions for the early detection of line degradation or failure. SHM systems are thus a key component in guaranteeing the integrity of FOWTs and reducing costs derived from the high safety-factors required in the mooring line's design. This goes in line with the new requirements of related standards, such as BSH [214], where the utilization of online monitoring of the support structures is mandatory.

6.3 Current Technologies/Methods

In contrast to inspection routines carried out at specific points in time as described in Section 5, SHM generally implies a continual information generation process. Furthermore, SHM systems aim at continuously monitoring the mooring line using off-the-shelf sensors and automatic fault detection procedures, whereas inspection requires specialized devices and qualified personnel, such as ROVs, divers and rope access technicians. This continuous monitoring complements periodical inspections, providing performance indicators, anomaly detections and mooring line loading conditions for fatigue assessment [35]. The SHM can trigger different alarm levels and actions related to them, such as an ad-hoc inspection or wind turbine stop by the control, for example.

Current monitoring techniques are largely based on recommendations from the Oil and Gas sector. The most common mooring line monitoring technologies include: sonar probes, inclinometers, load cells, and absolute positioning systems [35]. Some authors have also suggested ultrasonic guided waves and acoustic emissions as potential solutions [36][37]. Table 1 describes these technologies, including the advantages and disadvantages of each one.

Table 15: Mooring line monitoring technologies

Technology	Description	Advantages	Disadvantages	Suppliers
Load cells	This is arguably the most common technology. The goal is to directly measure the mooring line's tension to detect line failure, over loading, loss of tension, or to evaluate the line's fatigue life. Different solutions are available: instrumented pin in a shackle or other connecting link so that strain is measured in bending; specifically designed link so that a strain gauge is measuring axially, or it may be use of compression cells under chain stopper plates or winch footings [39]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Well-known and mature technology Certain standards already require tension monitoring [39] Direct measurement of each mooring line, aids localizing the faulty line Can be used for new and existing systems (this is more complicated in the case of inline load cells) [35] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reliability, accuracy and robustness are major issues [35] Expensive to build, install, and maintain Prone to damage during installation and operation [40] Difficult recalibration Inaccurate: certain effects significantly affect the measurement, such as friction losses or weather conditions [41] The full load range that the line is subjected to cannot be handled by the loadcell 	BMT, SMS, Fugro, Synectica, Ilex, Monitor, Pulse
Inclinometers	These sensors are used to measure mooring line angles. Generally, this measurement is used to compute line tension indirectly, using the catenary equation [41][38]. It can also predict line failure when the measured angle differs significantly from the expected one.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Well-known sensors Continuous monitoring Relatively low maintenance requirements Relatively cost-efficient sensor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Needs careful calibration to relate angle and mooring line load [35] Errors in the angle measurement result in significant errors in the estimated tension The static catenary equation, does not consider dynamic effects and non-linear behavior of the line tension [41] 	Seatools, BMT, SMS, Cybernetix, Pulse
Sonar	This technology transmits acoustic waves and processes the echoes of the mooring lines. Thus, measures the relative position of each mooring line and calculates the offset with respect to the expected position. Then, this difference in catenary profile is used to determine line faults [42][38]. With the measured catenary, this technology may also	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If can estimate tension and confirm that all lines are present [38]. If mounted on the platform, no battery packs or wireless transmission are required [38] In seabed sonars, a battery is required but there are no size restrictions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Early stage technology: relatively infrequent and non-mature technology for mooring line monitoring Limited ability to infer mooring line tensions [35] 	Tritech

	estimate the line's tension [38].	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can be used for new and existing systems • May cover the whole mooring system • Continuous monitoring 		
Positioning system	The platform position data, in combination with environmental conditions, is used to detect abnormal platform responses, such as offset from expected equilibrium position. These responses are then linked to the condition of the mooring lines [40][41].	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Widely used [40] • Reliable and cost-efficient sensors [41] • Sensors are installed on the platform: safe areas, no wireless connection required, reduced hardware requirements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Often requires a simulation model, which could be a challenge. • Also requires Metocean data to correlate • Measurement inaccuracies could lead to false positives. • Global technique, diagnosis level possibly limited to detection of mooring line failure 	Fugro, Honeywell, Kongsberg
Acoustic emissions	Acoustic emissions are the transient elastic energy waves generated by the rapid release of strain energy from a material undergoing micro-structural changes [43]. Thus, acoustic emissions reflect the material's internal stress redistribution, which occurs after cracks, plastic deformation, or friction [35]. Therefore, such acoustic emissions may be used to detect faults in mooring chains [36][37].	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can detect defects before installation [35] • Local methods which detects faults also in hardly accessible locations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early stage technology for mooring line monitoring • Is affected by surrounding environmental noises, adding extraneous noise to the signals. For a successful application of AE, signal discrimination and noise reduction are crucial • Costly technology • Effective only over a limited number of links, it would require several sensors per line [35] 	
Fiber optics for synthetic rope	This technology is based on sending laser pulses through an optical fiber embedded in the monitored line and measuring the return signal. Changes in signal's wavelength indicate strain changes, which can be measured [35][44].	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well established technology • Good quality signals • Fibers have relative low cost. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only valid for new synthetic rope systems, no retrofitting • Expensive technology, long-term fatigue issues in the fiber • Temperature and pressure compensation required • Sensor calibration 	

6.4 Gap Analysis

Considering the number, size, accessibility and hazardous conditions of mooring lines, local SHM methods do not seem a feasible solution, i.e. methods which assess local responses of the structure. Additionally, the crucial parameter to be monitored is the integrity of all mooring lines [41]. Therefore, global SHM methods are the preferred solution. However, currently used global SHM technologies, such as load cells, inclinometers, or positioning systems, have serious drawbacks which needs to be tackled (see **Table 15**).

In particular, the most commonly used method, i.e. line tension monitoring, is highly unreliable, costly, and prone to failures. Additionally, the current technology cannot measure the full range of the operational loads. Indirect measurements have been used as a potential alternative, but they also result in significant errors due to model simplifications and measurement error propagation.

Mooring line failure detection based on positioning systems is an attractive alternative with several advantages [41], such as (i) is highly cost effective, with minimum hardware and installation costs, (ii) sensors are located in safe areas, and (iii) no wireless transmission is required. This technology compares the measured position with the position predicted based on current Metocean conditions, and the position offset is related to line damage.

Several methods have been suggested to create a data-driven model that serves as a baseline for this comparison. Gumley discussed the use of neural networks, ARIMA models, and spatial correlation modelling (Kriging) to predict platform motion [45]. The use of neural networks in the context of deep learning was also discussed by Prislín [40], showing a high accuracy in the detection of mooring line's failure, but also a relatively high false alarm rate. Tracking trends of statistical parameters of the measured signals has also provided promising results [41]. Alternatively, similar numerical models have been used successfully for damage detection based on vibration data, such as NullSpace and autoregressive methods [46], which could be exploited also with position measurements.

The preliminary results of these techniques have shown promising results. However, these methods need to consider several fault scenarios, and a plethora of operational conditions, including Metocean conditions and seasonal variations. In addition, the dynamic behavior of each platform will be unique, and the successful extrapolation of data scenarios to other platforms is not guaranteed. Given the high customization of floating platforms, and the large number of conditions to be considered, it does not seem possible to obtain enough data to cover the training phase of the detection algorithms for all the possible operational and faulty conditions.

An interesting approach to tackle the different shortcomings identified in current technologies, is to combine the available measurements and a finely tuned physics-based model of the system. An accurate model of the FOWT could be used to obtain virtual sensors of the mooring line's tension, which can be compared with the measured ones to (i) update the model, and (ii) detect drifts in the expected tension that suggest line and/or sensor failure. In addition, this physics-based models could be used to obtain data scenarios to train the data-driven models under operational and faulty conditions which could not be measured otherwise.

6.5 Summary

SHM for monitoring the integrity of FOW substructures is in the development phase. First systems are available on the market, but there are reasonable doubts regarding their reliability and robustness, and local inspection remains necessary for making decisions on O&M. Based on the available technologies, the use of position monitoring systems seems the most promising candidate. However, the problem of effectively coping with varying environmental conditions and uncertainty hinders the accurate implementation of said method. A physics-based model which reliably represents the system is an interesting alternative to aid in the generation of data scenarios for data normalization, and in the estimation of variables of interest, such as mooring line tension.

7. Closed loop turbine control algorithms

7.1 Introduction

The concern with FOWTs is that when the wind turbine is operating in Region III, and the blade-pitch Proportional Integral (PI) controller is tuned as with onshore or bottom-fixed wind turbines, a coupling between the platform motion and the blade-pitch control can happen, known as platform negative damping [63][58].

Figure 48: Wind turbine power curve with control regions

This is due to the fact that the blade-pitch PI controller of the onshore and bottom-fixed wind turbines is tuned as vigorously as possible to regulate the generator speed close to the rated value and avoid speed excursions due to wind gusts, not taking into account the platform dynamics. Thus, when the wind flows, the thrust produced in the rotor of the FOWT generates a downwind motion of the system due to the platform's low hydrodynamic stiffness. During this motion, the relative wind speed observed by the wind turbine is less than the true wind speed, resulting in a generator slow-down. This is measured by the control unit, which tries to keep the generator speed at the rated speed, reducing the blade pitch and consequently increasing the thrust in the rotor and, hence, the downwind motion. Just the opposite happens when the FOWT is moving upwind. This effect can lead to large resonant platform motions, increasing blade, tower, platform and mooring line loads, well as deteriorating turbine performance.

One of the first and most complete studies done to tackle the effect of the platform negative damping in FOWTs was carried out in [58]. Three control alternatives were proposed to mitigate the barge type platform-pitch motions: feedback the tower top acceleration, blade-pitch-to-stall regulated control, and detuned blade-pitch-to-feather gains. The best result was achieved by detuning the blade-pitch-to-feather PI controller gains. Great reductions in the platform-pitch motion and in the load on the mechanical components were achieved. However, the rapidity of the regulation of the generator speed was degraded due to the reduction in the bandwidth of the controller.

7.2 Current Technologies/Methods

Van der Veen et al. [92] analysed the relative efficacy of the Collective Pitch Control (CPC) feeding back the nacelle motion. Yongoon et al. [65] ensured a good FOWT performance improvement with a nacelle motion feed-back control, reducing the blade and tower loads.

A similar strategy, but feeding back the nacelle velocity to the generator torque, was presented by Fischer in [93]. There, a few improvements were shown in the blade and drivetrain loads with the Non-Minimum Phase Zeros (NMPZ) approach, whereas the increases in the tower fore-aft and side-to-side loads were considerably increased. Wakui et al. [94] also feedback the nacelle velocity to the generator torque in [94]. However, the blade-pitch angle loop regulates the electric power instead of the generator speed. Few significant improvements were shown in the presented results, where the main drawback was the increase in the turbine torque activity due to the control regulation. Wang et al. designed an active disturbance rejection control feeding back the generator speed, but regulating the electric power of the FOWT in [95]. An adaptive control law was used to weaken the impact of platform-pitching movement and compensate the perturbations by a real-time estimation with a non-linear observer. The electric power output was improved with a Proportional and Derivative (PD) control and the platform-pitch motion was reduced compared to the presented baseline control. Wei et al. evaluated three different control strategies modifying the onshore baseline controllers in [96]. They concluded that all approaches have some drawbacks due to the lack of communication between the different SISO feedbacks. They proposed an improvement of the controllers, designing a model-based Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) controller.

Some other approaches can be found in the literature for the State-Feedback (SF) control and Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR). Namik et al. [97] designed a full SF control using a LQR for a barge FOWT system. Afterwards, they implemented a periodic Individual Pitch Control (IPC) and Disturbance Accommodating Control (DAC) in [98] for improving the performance of the FOWT reducing the effects of the incident wind and wave disturbances. In a more recent article [99], they proposed the IPC State Space (SS) control strategy and DAC, significantly reducing the barge platform-pitch, -roll and -yaw motions, and tower loads. However, the cost of these reductions was an extensive use of the blade-pitch actuator, where the blade-pitch rate was increased by 318% compared to the conventional CPC baseline controller.

Christiansen et al. [100] designed a SF controller with a state observer for the state estimation, wind speed estimator and LQR for optimal control. The overall improvement of the spar type FOWT model performance was achieved at the cost of the increased blade-pitch activity. The blade-pitch rate increases by 392% and the drivetrain torsion loads by 5%, in comparison to the baseline control. His next publication [101], based in the same control technique, includes the minimum thrust and constant generator speed strategy for stabilising the floating system. Deterioration in the generator speed regulation and power production were registered as well as increment in the platform-pitch oscillations of 20%. The last publication [102] based in the same control technique, but with an extended Kalman filter, shows the reduction of the wave disturbances on the onshore controller performance. A more developed SF controller was developed by Zuo et al. in [103]. They proposed an additional robust adaptive control with an advanced memory-based compensation module for the IPC. The power fluctuations, fatigue loads and platform vibrations were reduced in comparison to the conventional SF controller. Bagherieh et al. presented a sliding control technique for FOWT control in [104]. In comparison to the presented baseline controller, the generator speed deviation was improved whereas the platform-pitch motions were increased considerably, increasing the blade-pitch activity. In a more recent article [105], among the different control techniques compared, the best one in reducing the platform-pitch oscillations was the SF Linear Parameter-Varying (LPV) GS, while the best one for regulating the electric power was the LQR GS control technique. Lemmer et al. did a thorough system analysis in [106] considering the MIMO description including control inputs and disturbances in a

reduced FOWT model. They demonstrated that the LQR can significantly reduce the system response and attenuate the excitation from wave disturbances.

Two authors were found using a less common control technique for FOWTs, such as fuzzy logic. Yang et al. [107] used this technique to combine the DAC and the Model Predictive Control (MPC) algorithms. The DAC aimed at eliminating the effect of wind disturbances and the MPC to remove the effect of wave disturbances. The proposed control with IPC shows a better performance than the conventional CPC control results. Tahani et al. also used fuzzy logic in [108] for controlling the foundation directions of the VoulturnUS FOWT model, preventing additional movements and imbalances of the wind turbine.

Some other articles treating the MPC can also be found. Schlipf et al. Designed a MPC for a spar type floating FOWT in [109]. Although good improvements were shown in the shaft and blade loads, the main benefit was the reduction of the power and rotor speed standard deviation, by up to 90%. However, the cost of these improvements was a blade-pitch speed increase of about 228%. Raach et al. [110] continued in this topic, including the IPC technique to reduce the loads on the blade and minimise the yawing and pitching moments on the rotor hub. The blade loads were significantly reduced compared to the baseline controller. Chaaban et al. also presented the MPC but mounted on a barge platform in [111]. The results show a good overall performance improvement except in the generator power error, blade-pitch rate, and blade edgewise moment. Lemmer et al. [112] also present a study with the same control technique implemented for a double rated power capacity FOWT mounted on the TripleSpar platform. The results show that the MPC damps the tower-top and platform-pitch motion better than the presented baseline PI controller and reduces significantly the overshoot of the rotor speed.

The robust H-infinity control method (H1) is widely extended in FOWT systems too. Bakka et al. used the H1 feedback control technique with pole placement constraints in [113] and [114], with a LPV FOWT model. The generator speed and torque oscillations as well as the platform fore-aft displacement were reduced, but the blade-pitch activity was considerably increased. They used a similar technique in [115], but combining the H2 and H1 control techniques, resulting in a good rotor speed regulation and tower-top displacement mitigation but increasing considerably the blade-pitch activity as well. Betti et al. also used the H1 control technique for spar and TLP mounted FOWTs in [116] and [67], respectively. Navalkar et al. presented a combination of feedback and feedforward control using the H1 criterion in [117]. They implemented the Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) technology for the feedforward control enabling the wind turbine for the measurement of the incoming wind. Hara et al. presented experimental results from a scaled model FOWT using the H1 loop-shaping control in [118]. In comparison to the presented baseline PI control, the rotor speed regulation and platform-pitch oscillation were slightly improved whereas the blade-pith activity was increased considerably.

Lackner presented the Variable Power Pitch Control (VPPC) technique in [119] and [120]. This control technique consists in changing the generator speed set point to a larger value when the platform is pitching upwind, and vice versa. The platform motion is improved. However, the blade-pitch rate is considerably increased, by around 40%.

Other interesting articles can be found in the FOWT literature, not directly related with the negative platform damping control issue, but which some readers may find of interest. Han et al. studied a method to compute the movable range as well as the position control of FOWT in [121]. There are a couple of articles about a novel control technique for Region II. First, Bagherieh et al. used the blade-pitch control for this region in [66]. Second, Wang et al. used a variable torque control using an advanced Radial Basis Function (RBF) neural network in [122].

7.3 Gap Analysis

Work on the exploitation of novel sensors such as those proposed in this project is not abundant, for obvious reasons. More generally, the relationship between turbine control, platform position and mooring line loads requires careful study.

7.4 Summary

A wide variety of FOWT control techniques have been reported, which typically aim at mitigation of negative damping. The advent of accurate and reliable platform position sensors opens a similar field of study where control techniques may be aimed at mooring-line-related targets.

8. Line Tension Monitoring

8.1 Introduction

The number of floating structural solutions is expected to grow because of the deployment of offshore renewables industry in deep water areas. From the experience and available bibliography in the oil and gas industry, it is well-known that mooring lines are safety-critical systems. In offshore environment a breakage event of a mooring line might be catastrophic resulting in personnel safety issues, loss of production, and in some cases, failures could lead to important environmental damages. Consequently, there is a great interest in developing and implementing proper mooring system integrity management strategies, aided by reliable and accurate monitoring systems, to try to avoid both economic and environmental harm [123].

Mooring system integrity management involves aspects related to design philosophy, installation, monitoring and inspection, identification of anomalies and emergency responses. The integrity management strategy must consider the different failure modes and main degradation mechanisms that affect the mooring system: corrosion, fatigue, overloading, wear, and even design/manufacturing errors or damaged caused during the installation. However, the dynamic loading of the mooring lines and their related components due to waves, currents and wind gusts make a major consideration to the fatigue damage [126][127].

Offshore standards have published regulatory compliance and technical requirements for measuring mooring line tensions for moored floating structures [124][125][127]. In order to allow the assessment of mooring system integrity, moorings should be equipped with a calibrated system for measuring tension and a system to measure the line pay out if the operation requires mooring adjustment. At this regard, tension should be continuously displayed at each winch [124].

For structures endowed with thrusters, with the purpose of minimizing mooring lines' tensions, the floating platform should be equipped with a system to monitor its mooring line tensions. In addition, if their serviceability requirements impose displacement restrictions, position reference and heading should be monitored with the aim of being able to implement automatic thruster control and alarms under abnormal conditions and potential line failure. This mean should be suitable and redundant to cover the single-line failure condition [124]. Mooring line tensions should be monitored continuously with a sample rate of 1 Hz. Besides, historical records are to be stored and automatically logged at least 30 days back in time [128].

In order to interpret the severity of failures, standards establish a simple way to identify them. In general, mooring line tensions are compared to design limits. Unless otherwise specified, measuring ranges shall be between 10 and 70% of minimum breaking load. Exceeding these limits an alarm system is required. Normally, the less severe limit corresponds with the release of a warning, while the more severe limit will be used to activate alarms [128].

A more sophisticated approach is to use mooring line tension measurements, among other sources of information to assess the integrity of the mooring lines. However, where none of these is practicable, evaluation of mooring tension may be inferred from the positional information of floating structure. In this case, position must be continuously monitored [128][130]. In other cases, when continuous position and mooring lines' tension are available, measurements analysis can be suitable to confirm that, for instance, the low line tension measurement has been caused by an anchor line failure [128].

There are several measuring methods of mooring line tension in the industry based on direct measurement, such as load cells or shear pins, among others. In addition, indirect measurement methods are used for line tension monitoring, for instance, inclinometers and accelerometers, sonar

and recent techniques based on Global Navigation Satellite Systems (e.g. GPS) measurements in combination with numerical models that make it possible to calculate (or infer) mooring line tensions.

From all the available sensor technologies, the most used one is the load cell. This is a typical set up on vessels that use mooring systems, commonly seen on semisubmersibles and spars offshore structures, such as catenary mooring. However, experience has shown that accuracy, reliability and robustness are big issues of this technology [131]. Consequently, it is assumed by the industry that monitoring the mooring line tension or line angle together with met-ocean data should be performed to detect line failure, strength and fatigue analysis. [125].

The current research trend is to develop an integrated system, where a vast amount of data is acquired from a plurality of different kinds of sensors. The aim of the integrated system is to process large amount of information coming from sensors and numerical models (dynamics response, structural tension of the hull, met-ocean data, etc.) to assess the integrity of the mooring system and detect mooring line failures [126].

8.2 Current Technologies

This section describes the current available technologies with regard to mooring line tension monitoring, detailing its characteristics.

The mooring system monitoring methodologies that are currently used to measure the mooring line load, both directly and indirectly, are analyzed in the subsections hereafter: Load cells and Strain measurements (also called direct measurement systems), Inclinerometers, Fiber Optic sensors and those based on Global Navigation Satellite Systems, GNSS (known as indirect measurement systems).

Direct measurements refer to those taken explicitly of the object's characteristic that wants to be measured. An indirect measurement methodology, on the other hand, is an approach that uses alternative measurements and properties to find or infer the measurement of the desired characteristic.

8.2.1 Load Cell

The load cell is a sensor or a transducer that converts a load or force into an electronic signal. Load cells are formed by a metal body, usually made of aluminum, steel or stainless steel alloys, to which the tension meters have been secured. The body is very resistant but also minimally elastic. This elasticity gives rise to the term "spring element", which refers to the body of the load cell. When force is exerted on the load cell, the spring element deforms slightly and, unless overloaded, always returns to its original shape. As the spring element deforms, the tension meters also change shape, which results in an alteration of their electrical resistance that can be measured. The change in the resistance is proportional to the amount of force applied to the cell, and therefore the applied force can be calculated from the output signal of the load cell. The electric signal variation, depending on the specific sensor implementation (load cell and related electronics), can consist in a voltage, current or frequency change. Load cells are versatile devices that offer precise and robust performance in a wide range of applications. Under favorable operating conditions, as long as load cells are correctly installed and calibrated, accuracies in the order of 0.25% can be obtained [132][133].

There are many different kinds of load cells but the most common type of load cell used in industry is the strain gauge.

Figure 49: Working Principle of a load cell [133].

A strain gauge is a device that measures change in electrical resistance when a force is applied. A typical strain gauge is made up of very fine wire or foil, set up in a grid pattern in a way that produces a linear change in resistance when strain is applied along one axis. The strain gauge changes are different depending on type of load: tension or compression. Tension force causes the strain gauge to get thinner and longer, resulting in increased resistance. Compression force causes the strain gauge to get thicker and shorter, resulting in decreased resistance. The strain gauge is bonded to a thin backing (carrier), which is attached directly to the load cell enabling the strain of the load cell to be experienced by the strain gauge. The amount of deflection of the spring element must be minimal in order for it to deflect without permanent deformation. Calculations based on very small resistance changes in a strain gauge can be subjected to error because they are not highly accurate. To palliate this drawback and be able to reach better accuracies using load cells, multiple strain gauges are typically used together. Set in a Wheatstone bridge configuration (balanced when no load is applied) the overall change in resistance across all 4 strain gauges can be determined using Ohm's law (see Figure 49).

Regarding mechanical installation, the cells have to be properly mounted so that the load force is applied in the direction of the deformation of their sensing elements.. Otherwise it will not be possible to measure correctly the whole value of the acting force.

There are several types of strain gauge load cells, but subsea tension applications commonly use tension links and load pins [132][133]:

- Bending beam
- Pancake
- Single point shear beam load cell
- Double-ended shear beam
- Canister load cell
- S-type load cell
- Wire rope clamps
- Tension link load cell. These versatile load cells are specialized for measuring in-line tension forces. Available in a wide range of capacities, tension link load cells are also customizable for extremely heavy applications. These cells are often used for mooring and submersible testing, crane scales, and towing/pull force measurement [133].

- Load pin / shackle. Load pins replace a pin or axle on which force is applied. The design and structure of these cells are highly customizable and can be used at very high capacities. Load shackles are a type of load pin [133].

Figure 50: Subsea shear pin load cell (left) and tension link load cell (right) [134].

In theory, mooring line load monitoring is the most straightforward way to detect mooring line failures. Load cells are typically designed for a 25-year sub-sea life cycle because once installed they cannot be removed if failure arises. The continued and reliable operation is critical for the integrity of a mooring system especially in locations where high seas and hurricane forces can be expected.

To ensure compliance, they undergo rigorous examination and testing at each critical stage of the manufacturing process. Once approval of the design study is granted, the process continues with NDT examination of the raw material. This billet is often procured from a bespoke forging or limited production run. The testing and examination continues throughout the process with one of the final tests being the hydro test where the load cell is submerged in water for an extended period at a pressure above the operational depth [135][136].

Load cells are an existing and mature technology; however, experience has indicated that this measurement method has several drawbacks. The major issues in using the load monitoring system, especially underwater where access to the mooring line and instrument is very difficult, if not impossible, are accuracy, reliability and robustness. For systems exposed to long-term offshore loading conditions, power and signal transmission cables are areas of special weakness. Some systems have started to use wireless communications to solve it. Signal drift can be detected up to a point; however, it is not always possible to determine what is due to instrument drift versus what is a slow change in the real mooring line load. Another problem can be the system losses between the chain stopper where the load cell is installed and the mooring line tension away from the facility [135].

The frictional losses are difficult to ascertain and they may not be fixed over time. A new development in recent years is the use of in-line load cells with a load cell housed in a protective casing, making it better suited for offshore installation. Data transfer may be conducted via an acoustic transmitter or other wireless systems. As previously mentioned, load cells must be correctly installed to measure properly the mooring line forces, since otherwise effects such as friction may induce offsets or hysteresis. Wrong mounting may result in the cell reporting forces along undesired axis.

Another important issue is to subject the cell to loads which exceed its maximum rated value, because in this case, the material of the load cell may plastically deform and this may result in a signal offset, loss of linearity, difficulty with or impossibility of calibration, or even mechanical damage to the sensing element and its rupture.

The wires to the cell may develop high resistance, for example due to corrosion. Alternatively, parallel current paths can be formed by ingress of moisture. In both cases the signal develops offsets (unless all wires are affected equally) with the subsequent lost of accuracy.

The load cells also can be damaged by induced or conducted current. The fine resistors of the strain gauges can overstress and cause their damage or destruction. For welding operation in the vicinity of the cell it is suggested to disconnect the load cell and short all of its pins to the ground, nearby the cell itself. High voltages can break the electrical insulation between the substrate and the strain gauges.

Besides, it is important to consider the particularities of the application at hand. A load cell that is not well suited to the specific magnitude and type of pressure will have poor accuracy, resolution, and reliability.

Over time, load cells suffer from drift, ageing and misalignment errors; therefore, they need to be calibrated regularly to ensure accurate results are maintained [137]. ISO9001 and most other standards specify a maximum period of around 18 months to 2 years between re-calibration procedures, dependent on the level of load cell deterioration. The best practice for ensuring the most accurate measurements is considered annual re-calibration. Standard calibration tests will use linearity and repeatability as a calibration guideline as these are both used to determine accuracy. Calibration is conducted incrementally starting working in ascending or descending order. A five-step calibration process is usually sufficient for ensuring a device is accurately calibrated. Repeating this five-step calibration procedure 2-3 times is recommended for consistent results [138].

Usual loads in mooring FOWT are described in following table

Table 16: FOWT and OEC line mooring loads. Images from [168].

Project	FloatGen	Hywind	Meygen
Line monitoring	Unknown	Load Pin/shackle	Load Shackle
Photo			
Mooring Design Load	6000 KN	< 2000 Tonnes	2,5-10 Tonnes
Reference	[169]	[167]	Used for installation only [166]

Figure 51: Load cell arrangement in Hywind Scotland project [167]

In this sense, it should be mentioned that a large number of failures of this type of sensing element have been reported over the past few years in the offshore sector. Three examples are described hereafter:

Wave Dragon Case. The Danish company Wave Dragon developed and tested a device for obtaining wave energy in Denmark. After a storm the load cell broke, causing the device to drift. Fracture of the steel part due to inclusions has been pointed out as the cause. This affected the image of the company and also the image of marine energies.

Figure 52: Load cell failure used by WAVEDRAGON [139]

NOAA Case: The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration of the United States (NOAA) deployed a buoy measuring environmental parameters in the Atlantic Ocean. After 6 months of operation the connection cable between the load cell and the data acquisition system broke down due to fatigue loads [140][141].

IDERMAR Case: In the TIM project (INTELLIGENT FLOATING METEOROLOGICAL TOWER FOR CHARACTERIZATION OF WIND RESOURCES AND MARINE ENVIRONMENT) a floating mast was developed, manufactured and tested for the measurement of the wind resource. After a period of less than 1 year, the load cell stopped working after a storm passed over the system.

Figure 53: Load cells prior to failure [142]

Some Commercial Off-The-Shelf load cells are detailed in the following table:

Table 17: COTS load cell; Specification & Requirements [143][144]

Product type		Photo	Specification & Requirements
Scotload-Straininstall	Load Shackle		Rated load (kN): As required Proof load: 150% of rated load Ultimate breaking load: - Output: 4-20mA Accuracy: $\pm 1\%$ of full scale Excitation voltage: 10V (15V max) Bridge resistance: 700 Ohm Operating temperature range: -25 to +70°C Storage temperature range: -30 to +80°C of rated load/°C Environmental protection level: IP67/IP68
Scotload-Straininstall	Tension link load cell		Rated load (kN): As required Proof load: 150% of rated load Ultimate breaking load: 860 tonnes Output: 4-20mA Accuracy: $\pm 0.25\%$ of full scale Excitation voltage: 10V (15V max) Bridge resistance: 1000 Ohm Operating temperature range: -25 to +70°C Storage temperature range: -30 to +80°C of rated load/°C Environmental protection level: IP67/IP68
LCM Systems – LCM1791	Load Pin		Rated load (kN): 250 tonnes Proof load: 375 tonnes Ultimate breaking load: 860 tonnes Output: 2.2mV/V Accuracy: $<\pm 4\%$ of rated load Excitation voltage: 10V (15V max) Bridge resistance: 350 Ohm Operating temperature range: -20 to +70°C Storage temperature range: -10 to +70°C Environmental protection level: IP68 with connector mated to 200m
LCM Systems - LCM3511	Bow Shackle Load Cell		Rated load (kN): 85 tonnes Proof load: 127 tonnes Ultimate breaking load: >340 tonnes Output: 2.4mV/V Accuracy: $\pm 1\%$ of rated load >20te; $\pm 2\%$ of rated load <20te; Excitation voltage: 10V (15V max) Bridge resistance: 350 Ohm Operating temperature range: -20 to +70°C

<p>LCM Systems - LCM4570</p>	<p>Load Shackle</p>		<p>Rated load (tonnes): 12te Proof load: 150% of rated load Ultimate breaking load: >300% of rated load Output: 1.5mV/V (nominal) Accuracy: ±1% of rated load (typically) <±0.1% of rated load Excitation voltage: 2.5V Bridge resistance: 1000 Ohm Operating temperature range: -20 to +70°C</p>
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Table 18: COTS load cell; Prices and Industrial uses.

	Scotload-Strainstall	Scotload-Strainstall	LCM Systems - LCM4487	LCM Systems - LCM3511	LCM Systems - LCM4570
Product type	Load Shackle	Tension link load cell	Load Pin	Bow Shackle Load Cell	Load Shackle
Photo					
Price	55T - 2793€ 120T - 3968€ 150T - 4400€	50 T - 1316€ 120 T - 5350€	120T-1569€	120T - 4195€	120T - 3168€
Industrial uses	Strainstall's specialist mooring system starts monitoring at Hywind [145]	SSE utilises SmartLoad® load monitoring technology during power cable installation [146]	Load Pins for Anchor Chain Load Measurement in Norway [147]	-	Mooring line monitoring of fish farm tanks [148]

A summary of the advantages and disadvantages of load cells is shown in the following table:

Table 19: Summary of advantages and disadvantages of a load cell.

	Advantages	Disadvantages
Load cell	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has been used in a wide number of applications - Rugged and compact construction - No moving parts - Can be used for static and dynamic loading 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The cells have to be properly mechanic mounted - Measurement could not be reliable especially when the mooring line load is not very high - Many other factors affect the output of the measurement, such as friction,

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highly Accurate - Wide range of measurement - Long time, very well used method for load measurement. - Relatively simple system 	<p>temperature, signal drafting or recalibration.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Durability of transmission cables - It is important to subject the cell to loads under its maximum rating to avoid plastic deformation - Calibration is a tedious procedure
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8.2.2 Inclinometers

An inclinometer is an instrument used for measuring angles (attitude) of an object with respect to gravity vector's direction. There are different technologies and operating principles when it comes to inclinometers. Regarding technologies, one of the most cost-effective and commonly used technologies is based on Micro Electro-Mechanical Systems (MEMS). MEMS technology implements accelerometers, typically manufactured from silicon, that are able to measure the effect of gravity, as well as the effect of induced accelerations in dynamic applications.

MEMS inclinometers designed for static application (or quasi static) use a tiny mass suspended in an elastic support structure. The operating principle consist in sensing slight displacement of the tiny mass caused by device tilt through a change in the capacitance between the mass and the supporting structure. Then, tilt angle is derived from the measured capacitances.

Figure 54: Principle of a MEMS sensor: 1 proof mass with; 2 electrodes, 3 springs, 4 fixed electrodes [149].

For dynamic applications, MEMS inclinometers are based on the piezoresistive properties of silicon. In this case, the piezoresistive effect is used to measure the deformation of the structure, from which acceleration can be derived through Newton's second law of motion [170].

Inclinometers also known as tilt indicators, tilt sensors, tilt meters, slope gauges, gradient meters, gradiometers, level gauges, level meters, declinometers, or pitch & roll indicators. Inclinometers measure both inclines (positive slopes) and declines (negative slopes), and they can typically use three different units of measure: degrees, percent, and topo. A tilt sensor is often designed to measure the tilting of a reference plane in two axes. In contrast, a full motion sensor would use at least three axes and often additional sensors (e.g. magnetometers and/or gyroscopes). These tilt or level meters determine the pitch and/or roll angle and output these values via the appropriate electrical interface [149].

A simple inclinometer could measure mooring line angles. Many mooring systems have been fitted with inclinometers that are designed to derive line tensions and/or to detect line breakages. It can be

used for catenary systems to derive an approximation of the mooring line (quasi-static) tension by measuring the angle of the mooring line at or near the top connection to the platform (Ukani, et al, 2012). The positions of the anchor and the floating unit must be known in order to get the line tension converted from the angle measurement. For this application, each inclinometer typically contains its own battery, memory, and acoustic emitter. The measured data is transmitted to receivers and then hard-wired to the computer display [150].

Figure 55: Mooring chain with inclinometer supported in custom mounting bracket [151].

However, the dynamic and nonlinear effects are not included in the calculated tension from angle [135]. An alarm indicating a mooring line failure would be raised when the angle goes outside the predefined limits. In calm weather, if any of the mooring line angles has changed to a significant extent, it might be interpreted as a line failure. Some inclinometer systems have been reported to provide poor reliability records, where some of them generated spurious readings and some failed to work.

When the line is very slack, small changes in tension will introduce significant angle variations. When the line gets tighter, the angle changes less significantly. However, inclinometers have the same accuracy over the entire range of fairlead angle and with accuracies better than 0.1 degrees can still be used to resolve the fairlead angle and thus the quasi-static tension [152].

One of the biggest problems that inclinometers have historically had is its robustness. The instrumentation components are often fully exposed to the seawater and harsh environment in which the mooring lines are located. Some of the issues that have caused malfunctions of a system are corrosion, water ingress, cable connections, acoustics, and battery life [150].

The general accuracy of an inclinometer varies according to the type of its sensing element and the technology used but, in summary, the factors that influence the use of inclinometers are:

- Gravity.
- Temperature (drift), zero offset, linearity, vibration, shock, cross-axis sensitivity, acceleration/deceleration.
- Calibration and compensation of deterministic errors.
- A clear line of sight between the user and the measured point is needed (for wireless data output systems).
- A well-defined object is required to obtain the maximum precision.
- The angle measurement precision and accuracy is limited to slightly better than one arcsec.

Highly sensitive electronic inclinometer sensors can achieve an output resolution of 0.0001°, although depending on the technology and angle range, it may be limited to 0.01°. The true or absolute accuracy of an inclinometer sensor is the total combined error, which is a combination of the above factors. Thus, the accuracy of electronic inclinometers can typically vary from ± 0.01 – 2° depending on

the sensor and the situation. Generally, under ambient (not controlled) conditions, the accuracy is generally decreased and significantly related to the linearity specification of the sensor.

Some popular COTS inclinometers, in some cases in combination with load cells, are detailed in Table 20 and Table 21:

Table 20: Inclinometers COTS; Specification & Requirements [153][154][155][156][157].

	Type	Photo	Specification & Requirements
Seatools - SINCLINO 200	Single-axis subsea inclination sensor		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Designed to withstand harsh operating conditions. Two different sensors: sensor A is executed with magnetic damping and is suitable for vibration-intensive environments. Sensor B provides extremely high accuracy levels and is designed for applications that are not or less subjected to vibration. - inclination angles ; Sensor A: 360°, Sensor B: $\pm 70^\circ$ - Data output formats; Sensor A: 4 – 20 mA, 0 – 5 V, and RS 232. For sensor B: 4 – 20 mA, 0 – 5 V, RS 232, and RS 485.
Seatools - TWINCLINO 1000	Dual-axis subsea inclination sensor		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Twinclino 1000 sensor can be executed with two different sensor types. Sensor A is characterized by extreme accuracy of up to $< 0.051\%$ F.S. Sensor B is a cost-competitive sensor, which achieves average measurement accuracies of up to $< 0.28\%$ F.S. - For sensor A, inclination angle: $\pm 90^\circ$. For sensor B, inclination angle: $\pm 80^\circ$. - Sensor A: 4 – 20 mA or a 0 – 5 V. Sensor B: 0 – 10 V, 4 – 20 mA, RS232. - Material housing: Stainless steel 316L - Weight in air 13 kg (excl. 5.5 kg mounting plate) - Operational temperature range -20°C - $+50^\circ\text{C}$
Seatools - MoorMate	System based on the inclination measurement by means of an inclination sensor		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 20 years design lifetime (subsea) - 5 years maintenance interval - Able to survive FPSO (mooring line) installation operations - The system generates an alarm if one, two, or all three measurements indicate a mooring-line failure - The system can be further extended with an underwater camera system allowing for visual inspection of the mooring lines

<p>Technip & Cybernetix - ALLMS</p>	<p>Modular system made of standard components.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For breakage or overstress alarms, top angles are measured by inclinometers. For stress cycling monitoring, load cells or vibrating wires (extension/compression measurements) measure parameters that enable tension calculations. - ALLMS is suitable for all types of moored floating facilities
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Table 21: Inclinometers COTS; Price and Industrial uses.

	Seatools - SINCLINO 200	Seatools - TWINCLINO 1000	Seatools - MoorMate
Product type	Single-axis	Dual-axis	System based on the inclination measurement
Photo			
Price (aprox.)	1210€	2386€	Unknown
Industrial uses	Seatools to Supply Dredging Monitoring Sensors [158]	-	In 2018 Seatools successfully delivered a remote offshore monitoring system for the Ocean Cleanup [155]

A summary of the advantages and disadvantages of inclinometers is shown in the following table:

Table 22: Summary of inclinometers advantages and disadvantages

	Advantages	Disadvantages
Inclinometer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It can be used in all types of mooring systems, most suitable for catenary system for derived line tension - Direct measurement of line angle and not affected by other parameters. - Relatively simple system with low cost. - Signal could be transmitted acoustically. - Low maintenance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has been used in a limited number of applications - Can only derive quasi static mooring line tension. - Dynamic and nonlinear effects are not included. - Need careful calibration for the model of mooring line angles and mooring line load. - Low robustness. - Water ingress, corrosion, cable connections, acoustics and battery life.

8.2.3 Strain measurements

Although it is an immature technique which is still under development with regard to mooring line tension monitoring, it is also interesting to mention the existing methods for direct deformation measurement. Optical fiber strain gauges operate on very different principles than those that govern traditional electrical strain gauges. They are based on fiber Bragg gratings (FBGs). In simple terms, a fiber Bragg grating is a microstructure created by modifying a standard single-mode telecom fiber, germanium doped, with a UV laser. This microstructure, typically a few millimeters long, creates a periodic variation in the refractive index of that optical fiber. As light travels along the fiber, the Bragg grating reflects a very narrow range of wavelengths; all of the other wavelengths are transmitted through the grating. The center of this band of reflected wavelengths is known as the Bragg wavelength. Under stress, the period of an FBG increases due to the physical stretching or compression of the optical fiber.

This change results in a shift in the Bragg wavelength of the reflected signal, which is then detected and recorded by the interrogator (i.e., data acquisition system) [159].

Figure 56: The principle underlying the operation of fiber Bragg grating (FBG) strain gauges. [159].

Bragg fiber gratings are not only sensitive to deformation but also to temperature, which allows them to be used to control this parameter in other applications. In this way, the effect of temperature on the strain sensor can be compensated by combining a temperature sensor with a strain sensor. FBG-based optical fiber strain gauges offer a variety of advantages over electrical strain gauges. For example, they provide long-term signal stability and system durability. The connection leads are much lighter than copper conductors because optical fibers are much thinner and lighter. Distance and cable length have virtually no impact on measurement accuracy; because optical fiber based systems experience only minimal signal attenuation, the integrity of the data remains high, even if the data acquisition system must be located several kilometers away. A single measuring lead allows connecting many sensors with different base wavelengths, reducing the level of wiring effort required. The use of FBG sensors allows for drastic reductions in the amount of cabling a monitoring system requires. Installation and network complexity is reduced due to the "multiplexing" concept; Ability to

connect many different types of optical sensors to a single optical fiber. They are also well suited for use in harsh environments and safe for use in potentially explosive atmospheres and high voltage areas. In addition to their EMI/RFI immunity, they offer high resistance to degradation due to water and humidity, salt, temperature extremes, and high pressure (up to 400 bar) [159].

Ractliffe patented one of the first designs using optical fibers for condition monitoring of fiber ropes [160][161]. The inventor proposes continuous monitoring to identify high local stresses. To do this, optical fibers are embedded into the strands of a fiber rope. In 1993 the authors D'Agostino, Barrick and Williams created a patent with the proposal of another design where the strains and stresses are determined by monitoring the fiber light transmissive and reflective properties. The inventors propose to use a reference pattern measured when the rope is new, and compare it with patterns measured during use. The changes in patterns over time then serves as condition indicators [162].

Examples of COTS inclinometers, some of them combined with load cells, are detailed in Table 23 and Table 24 below:

Table 23: Fiber Optic Strain Sensors COTS; Specification & Requirements [164].

Type		Photo	Specification & Requirements
HBM - FS62	Optical Strain Sensors		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strain sensors designed to be glued to surfaces and materials, spot welded to structures and components, attached or directly cast into concrete wet mix. - Measurement range: Up to $\pm 5000 \mu\text{m/m}$ - Operation temperature: -20 to $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ - Protection Class: Surface and Embedded: IP68
HBM - OL/OL-W	Optical Strain Gauge		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strain gauges designed to be glued (OL) or spot welded (OL-W) to structures and materials. - Measurement range: $\pm 10000 \mu\text{m/m}$ - Bending radius: OL: $>2.5\text{cm}$ OL-W: $>30\text{cm}$ - Operation temperature: OL: -10 to $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ OL-W: -40 to $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
HBM - FS22DI-ST	Interrogator		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Optoelectronic instrument which allows the reading of optical fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors in static and dynamic monitoring applications. - Can measure a large sensing network composed by various types of sensors connected along multiple fibers, by acquiring data simultaneously and at different sampling rates.

Table 24: Optical strain sensors COTS; Price and Industrial uses [164].

	HBM - FS62	HBM - OL/OL-W	HBM - FS22DI-ST
Product type	Optical Strain Sensors	Optical Strain Gauge	Interrogator - Data acquisition system
Photo			
Price	215€	Optical fiber with multiple Fiber Strain Gauges: 1700€	10000-20000€ (Depending on characteristics like the number of optical connectors)
Industrial uses	<p>Although there is still no application of this type of sensors to mooring lines, other industrial applications that have been found for this type of sensors are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tunnels Structural Monitoring - Wind Blade Load Monitoring - Monitoring of fiber ropes - Characterization of Railway Traffic and its Effect on Structures <p>Monitoring Method for The Rope Of A Lifting Device [165].</p>		

A summary of the advantages and disadvantages of Fiber Optic Strain Sensor is shown in the following table:

Table 25: Summary of Fiber Optic Strain Sensors advantages and disadvantages [163].

	Advantages	Disadvantages
Fiber Optic Strain Sensor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is compact in size. - It does not contaminate their surroundings and is not subject to corrosion. - Electrical Passiveness - Resistant to high temperatures and chemically reactive environment - Electromagnetic Immunity: immune to radio frequency interference (RFI) and electromagnetic interference (EMI). - It is highly sensitive. - It is easy to install and maintain. - It is reliable. - It offers longer life. - Multiplexing and distribution Capabilities of sensors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is thermal sensitive. - It is difficult to demodulate wavelength shift. - It is difficult to discriminate wavelength shift due to temperature and strain separately. - Optical fibers are fragile and prone to damage during use. Hence care should be taken while use. - High cost due to the data acquisition system - Unfamiliarity to the end user

8.2.4 Sonar

Sonar (Sound Navigation and Ranging) is based on sound propagation and it is used in a plurality of applications: military, civilian and scientific applications. Sonar has been used for exploring and mapping the ocean, taking advantage of the fact that sound waves travel farther in the water than radar and light waves do. There are two types of sonar; passive and active [209]. While passive sonar systems are used to detect noise from marine objects or marine life (since unlike active sonar, passive sonar does not emit its own signal), active sonar systems are used to measure the distance to objects underwater. In active sonar systems transducers emit an acoustic signal or pulse of sound into the water. If an object is in the path of the sound pulse, the sound bounces off the object and returns an “echo” to the sonar transducer. If the transducer is equipped with the ability to receive signals, it measures the time of flight (time between the emission of the sound pulse and its reception) and the strength of the signal. This way active sonars can be used to determine the range and orientation of an object [209].

8.2.4.1 Application to mooring lines

Sonar-based system can be used for real time feedback on the status of mooring lines. Some sonar heads can provide a 360-degree view through images that provide valuable information of relative distances of objects from the sonar head. The primary aim of the sonar technology applied to mooring lines is to measure the relative position of each of the lines and calculate the offset of the measured point to the expected position. In fact, the expected position can be defined as an envelope. This provides the ability to detect abnormal situations which are likely to be associated with damages or failures [208] [209].

Figure 57: Sonar head deployed below the hull
[209]

Figure 58: Tritech's sonar graphical interface
[209]

On the other hand, the sonar technology can be used to measure catenary, and thus estimate the line's tension [35]. However, the maturity of such a technology for real time estimation on mooring line tension is still under development. Moreover, even though it can be applied to most types of installation, it is more suited to turret moored systems since spread moored semi-submersible would require more complex installation with more sensors and communication systems with higher bandwidth and more nodes.

Two different types of sonar installation can be used to monitor mooring lines' tensions:

- Hull mounted sonar are used to estimate tensions from declination measurements
- Seabed sonar can provide information on the shape of the catenary allowing the estimation of tensions.

8.2.4.2 Hull Mounted Sonar

Mounting a sonar head under the hull of a floating platform and have it looking downwards as shown in the following picture can be used to locate the mooring lines at a short distance outboard of their connection point. These measurements can be used to derive the angle of the mooring line as it leaves its connection point. As with inclinometers, mooring line angle information is used to estimate mooring lines' tensions in a fast and easy way by the software implementation of look-up tables that relate angles with tensions [207].

Figure 59: Hull mounted sonar system arrangement [207].

Hull mounted sonar strategy requires the use of additional sensors that provide information of the 3D position of the mooring line connector and 3D position of the sonar head, as well as the heading of the floating platform. Hull mounted sonar approach presents several advantages:

- Sound echoes received by the transducer will be strong since distance is limited, leading to accurate position measurements.
- The angle of incidence of the sound waves can be close to perpendicular, contributing to better measurements.
- Battery packs are not required as fixed wiring for power and signal can be routed direct back to the floating unit.

On the other hand, some drawbacks exist:

- The deployment of the system requires the intervention of divers or ROVs.
- A structure on the hull or ad-hoc fastening solution is needed for attachment of the sonar heads [207].
- Fixed wiring for power and communication is susceptible to failure in long deployments.
- Time lag between images from different sensors needs to be addressed

8.2.4.3 Seabed Sonar

A sonar head array installed on the seabed can provide full view of all mooring lines through its sonar imaging technology. Catenary shapes and location can be obtained and used to derive mooring lines' tensions, as well as to confirm that all mooring lines are in place (no failures occurred).

Figure 60: Seabed mounted sonar arrangement [207].

Seabed installed sonar presents several advantages:

- Its deployment is straightforward since it can be done from the floating unit itself without the need for a ROV/diver.
- Battery life can be extended as there are no size/weight restrictions
- It is easily accessed by ROV, either for substitution or indeed latching on of a lifting sling for recovery.
- A full 360 degree spread of sonar beams is not necessary as the sonar transducer is on the floor and pointing to the surface.
- Allows simultaneous mapping of all mooring lines (no synchronization is required).

On the contrary, the main drawback is the need for sophisticated hydro acoustic modem technology to transmit the measured data to the floating unit.

To conclude, the main sonar technology advantages and disadvantages are summarized in the following table:

Table 26: Summary of sonar advantages and disadvantages [208], [206]

Technology	Advantages	Disadvantages
Sonar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Well proven technology in ocean applications - If can estimate tension and confirm that all lines are present. - If mounted on the platform, no battery packs or wireless transmissions are required. - In seabed sonars, a battery is required but there are no size restrictions. - Can be used for new and existing systems. - May cover the whole mooring system. - Continuous monitoring. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Early stage technology: relatively infrequent and non-mature technology for mooring line monitoring. - Limited ability to infer mooring line tensions (only applicable to catenaries). Its use is mainly focused on failure detection [208] - Expensive sensor technology - Needs a very high communication bandwidth. This requirement implies the need for communication cable or expensive hydro acoustic modem when real time monitoring is needed.

8.2.5 Global Navigation Satellite System

GNSS receivers track and process the signals in space broadcasted by the different constellation's satellites. This information can be used by a wide range of applications although most of them rely directly on the navigation solution generated by the receiver (i.e. position, velocity and time) [171]. This solution is computed by the receiver from the distance of the receiver to the tracked satellites, obtained from the propagation time through space of the signals according to the satellite and receiver local clocks. Before it can be used for the triangulation of the user position, these rough estimations of the range to each satellite need to be corrected to account for a number of phenomena, such as the effect of the troposphere and ionosphere, relativistic effect, etc.

Figure 61: GNSS navigation working principle.

The specific receiver architecture depends on the GNSS system and frequencies used, but they have in common the antenna, that captures the radiofrequency signals, a front-end to down-convert, filter, amplify and digitize the signals, a baseband signal processing module, which acquires and tracks the signals and, finally, the application processing engine, that generates the navigation results required by the application [172]:

Figure 62: GNSS receiver architecture.

The selection of a receiver type is tightly linked to the target application, since different receivers yield different performances for different scenarios. The qualification and quantification of the error measurements depending on the receiver accuracy is an ongoing debate nowadays.

Most commonly extended mooring monitoring devices, as shown in previous sections, are mainly based on inclinometers and load cells, while GNSS technology has commonly been used to try to detect mooring lines' failures [181]. The use of load cells is so widespread in the O&G industry that are the only considered option for mooring lines and anchors tension measurements in offshore mooring

standards [173], relegating angle measurements to so called special applications during installation, when continuous monitoring is not required.

Figure 63: Excursion Monitoring System (EMS) from RUP LTD [186].

Figure 64: Position Monitoring System (PMS) installed on the on wheelhouse of an FPSO [181].

Mean offset due to single broken mooring line

FPSO position change after line failure

Expected position envelopes for different sea states

FPSO position offset over time

Figure 65: Example of other studies of using GNSS for line failure detection [181].

Attempts to carry out comparisons between floating platform motion (measured with GNSS technology) and met-ocean conditions (wind, wave and current conditions) try to give feedback on the integrity of the mooring system, but this analysis needs to be done case by case and consequently implies high costs and long lead times.

Positioning and navigation solutions in safety critical applications are traditionally constrained by regulations and standards (e.g. aviation). However, the emergence of new applications that still lack of regulations has imposed a very fast pace of development resulting in innovative solutions. Although many of these solutions are based on a plurality of sensor technologies and a sensor fusion approach (for instance, the hybridization of GNSS and inertial sensors is a common practice in many application domains) a standalone solution based exclusively on GNSS technology present several benefits such as: no need for recalibration, no moving parts, robust technology that can withstand harsh environmental and operational conditions.

GNSS precise and robust positioning and navigation can be achieved through dual, triple or quadruple frequency receivers and two major techniques: Real Time Kinematic (RTK) and increasingly Precise Point Positioning (PPP). Multi-frequency receivers offer significant advantages over single frequency

receivers in terms of achievable accuracy and also in terms of robustness and resistance to jamming and multipath.

Regarding GNSS precise positioning techniques, RTK and PPP, each has their advantages and disadvantages. RTK has been used extensively over the years and can provide positioning of high accuracy (a few cm) with rapid convergence in both real-time and post processing mode. However, it has two main drawbacks. The first is the need for a dedicated base station, which means that the user needs to set-up their own local base station or make use of existing reference stations that provide real-time corrections (with a service charge). Additionally, there is performance degradation with the distance between base station and users, and so if there are no nearby reference stations or the application covers a wide area (both situations might be representative for FOW Farms) then the performance of RTK is drastically limited.

RTK drawbacks can potentially be overcome through the use of the precise point positioning (PPP) technique. PPP is an efficient absolute positioning technique that uses the pseudorange and carrier phase measurements from a single receiver, together with the precise orbit and clock corrections and their appropriate models (earth tides, ionosphere effects, troposphere effects, phase wind-up, etc.), in order to compute a precise solution. This removes the need for a local reference station and means that PPP is applicable anywhere in the world as the accuracy is not dependent on distance from a reference station. However, PPP also has some limitations. One is that it relies on external correction products (i.e. precise orbit and clock products) in order to get the best performance.

There are some freely available correction products (e.g. provided by the International Global Navigation Satellite System Service – IGS) [175], but they require an internet connection in order to download the most suitable products for real time computations (Ultra-Rapid products [176]). It is also possible to obtain these corrections in the end-user receiver from geostationary telecommunication satellites, through service providers at a specific cost (e.g. VERIPOS, TerraStar, OmniSTAR and StarFire), eliminating the need for additional cellular connectivity or base station. Nevertheless, the main limitation of the PPP technique is its requirement of a relatively long convergence time for precise positioning (at least compared to RTK) that has prevented its use in real time applications. In order to achieve the best results in terms of accuracy and convergence time a PPP Integer Ambiguity Resolution (PPP-AR) is usually conducted. The three main available ways to resolve the PPP ambiguities include the uncalibrated phase delay (UPD) model [177], the integer phase clock model [178], and the decoupled clock model [179]. Nevertheless a typical convergence time of 20 min is still required for PPP whereas RTK can fix integer ambiguities and converge to the best solution within a few minutes or less (at least for short baselines).

Two important technological breakthroughs have provided the opportunity to develop improved PPP solutions in terms of accuracy, convergence time and cost. Firstly, there are currently four Global Navigation Satellite Systems: GPS (USA), GLONASS (RF), BeiDou (PRC) and Galileo (EU) with either full operational capability (FOC) or nearing FOC status, with the two most recent constellations due to complete deployment by 2020. As a result there were already over 100 GNSS satellites in orbit as of December 2017. This way multi-GNSS PPP-AR approaches achieve dramatic reductions on the convergence time [180]. The Three Carrier Ambiguity Resolution (TCAR) has been used traditionally to improve the integer ambiguity resolution performance.

Secondly, GNSS receivers' manufacturers are launching multi-frequency receivers for the mass market [181]. After many years of use limited to professional or governmental users (mainly because of high cost), the first dual frequency chipset for the mass market (i.e. for smartphones and IoT devices) was launched in 2017 (incorporating L1/E1 and L5/E5a). Several more are available in 2019.

These architectures have opened the door to high-precision techniques at low costs due to the high-volume and the related scale economies. However, such integration of multi-frequency and multi-constellation measurements results in several parameters that can be considered as biases (inter-frequency and inter-constellation) that need to be modelled and estimated online.

The following list summarizes the more relevant aspects of using GNSS for line tension monitoring, including the main advantages and disadvantages of this approach, in comparison with direct measurement methods, currently the de-facto standard:

- There is no need to place sensors or any other equipment in hazardous areas.
- It is not required any wireless transmission of signals between the sensing element and the processing unit.
- It is a self-contained sensor (there is no need to connect to other sensors to complete its functionality for this application, though it is usually combined with inertial sensors for their complementary features).
- Its associated hardware, cabling, installation and maintenance costs are minimum.
- The sensor is composed of very few components, with no moving parts, which has a very positive impact on reliability and sensor longevity.
- It does not require any calibration (just the selection of the proper point(s) of the floating structure to register).
- As a consequence of all the above, GNSS monitoring systems are easy to install and maintain.
- A single sensor GNSS is enough for position monitoring of a point in the structure. Additional sensors could be used for heading (2) or complete attitude determination (3).
- It requires a relatively low initial inversion (of course, depending on the required performance, but compared to the other types of technology used for mooring monitoring GNSS is definitely cheap).
- Low recurrent costs, since the maintenance and calibration requirements are nearly none.

In the following table a comparison of some commercial-of-the-shelf receivers is shown:

Table 27: Commercial of-the-self GNSS receiver comparison (medium grade)

GNSS receiver	Price	Features
Novatel OEM 7700 	5 K€ 6 K€ (with access to corr. service)	Multi-constellation: all Multi-frequency: all available Tracking channels: 555 L-band channel: Yes Corr. Services: Terrastar Interference mitigation Accuracy*: 1.2 m (L1/L2)
Septentrio AsteRx4 	5 K€	Multi-constellation: all Multi-frequency: all available Tracking channels: 544 L-band channel: Yes, dual Corr. Services: Marinestar Dual antenna (heading) Integrity monitoring Interference mitigation Accuracy*: 1.2 m

Septentrio AsteRx- m2		3 K€	Multi-constellation: all Multi-frequency: all available L-band: Yes Corr: Sapcorda ready Integrity monitoring Interference mitigation Accuracy*: 1.2 m
Trimble BX992		4 K€	Multi-constellation: all Multi-frequency: all available L-Band: Yes, Tracking channels: 544 L-band channel: Yes, dual Corr. Services: Omnistar, Trimble RTX Integrity monitoring Multipath mitigation Accuracy*: 1 m
NVS NV08C		200 €	Multi-constellation: GLONASS, GPS, GALILEO, BEIDU, SBAS Multi-frequency: L1, L2 Tracking channels: 96 L-band: No Corr. Services: No Integrity monitoring Multipath mitigation Accuracy*: 2.5 m
<i>* Horizontal accuracy, standalone (without correction services, RTK, etc.)</i>			

8.2.6 Integrated Monitoring System

An integrated monitoring system (IMS) may include systems that monitor many different parameters and onboard forecast systems. The monitoring system monitors environmental conditions, such as wind, wave and current, FPS motions, mooring line angle and load. The forecast system may include the prediction of FPS motions and mooring line load. The data acquisition system uses a central server onboard to collect, process, and store the data from the various instruments and sensors (e.g. Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS), Inertial Measurement Units (IMU), Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (ADCP), inclinometers, accelerometers, Fiber Bragg Gratings (FBG), etc.). The system is relatively expensive and requires a lot of data processing [183].

Nevertheless, there are some example cases of the application of relatively simple versions of IMS to FPSO, in which only the vessel's position and the mooring lines angles are being measured. The mean mooring line tensions are derived in those cases using the measured mooring line angles and vessel's position data (e.g. Strainstall, Scanmatic, BMP...).

Table 28: IMS – GNSS comparison.

	GNSS	Integrated system
Maturity	Has been used in a number of applications	Has been used in a limited number of applications
Intent	To monitor and measure FPSO locations and hence to derive the mooring line load	Monitor and detect mooring line overloading, failure, and provide operation advisory
Application	All types of mooring systems	All types of mooring systems
Deployment	New and existing systems	New and existing systems
Advantage	Easy to install and relatively low cost. Equipment on board the vessel and easy to maintain	Comprehensive system for real time monitoring and provide advisory for operations
Disadvantage	The relationship between vessel's position and mooring line load needs to be carefully studied to have a clear understanding between the measured positions and mooring line load. Environment measurement (wind, wave, and current) may be necessary	Relatively expensive; A lot of data processing; The system is relatively new and the effectiveness of the advisory system is not known yet

8.3 Gap Analysis

Many of the currently installed systems on offshore industry have been reported to be insufficient regarding accuracy and reliability, in this respect current technologies show a questionable effectiveness. The integration of different technologies could lead to a technically feasible solution, although an integrated mooring line tension monitoring system valid for all kinds of floating platforms does not exist, since each monitoring solution depends on the specific floating system. This fact implies a considerable increase of cost and lead time, since any system should be designed ad-hoc [183].

Gaps and challenges of the mooring line tension technologies are summarized in the following paragraphs.

8.3.1 Direct in-line Tension Monitoring- Load Cell

The load cell is the most mature and simplest method for line tension monitoring, however in practice it has been found a lack of success when used in mooring system monitoring, especially for permanent deep water deployments. A particular weakness using load cell monitoring system exposed long time on offshore conditions is the robustness and reliability of signal transmission cables.

Load cell installed in chain-stoppers or winches are typically very poor. Corrosion, fouling, waste, mud and temperature effects are examples of agents that can be present in the chain and those can cause frictions whose losses are difficult to determine, being prejudicial for sensitivity of load cells. In a number of cases these deviations can be quantified as more than 100% [182].

Investigating new specific methods for offshore facilities to address the lack of direct line tension monitoring is crucial to effectively guaranty of life service of floating structures. A new approach has appeared recently based on acoustic transmitter data or load cell housed in a protective casing [185].

Another observed gap is that technology is not able to detect low load with accuracy. Experience has shown for anchor handling that very high line pulls are required to drag large diameter chain through the sea-bed [183].

8.3.2 Indirect In-line Tension Monitoring – Inclometers

Indirect line tension monitoring seems a great way to determine mooring line load in real time. The technology consists in real time prediction of mooring line load based on continuous measurements of mooring line angles (i.e. being them measured with inclinometers or sonar sensors). Nowadays, there are a limited number of applications and hence it is an immature technology whose reliability is still questionable. A particular technical gap has been known when the system is operating in real condition. It is necessary to be addressing a good performance of mooring system model for good load prediction [184].

Besides, indirect tension measurement based on angles is limited to catenary mooring system (chains), where mooring dynamics have a direct impact on the mooring lines' angles. Tensions can be derived from catenary equations or through look-up tables obtained in simulations. However, there are floating platforms such as Tension Leg Platform (TLP) that have taut mooring configurations, which do not exhibit remarkable changes in mooring lines' angles when tension varies. This is a clear limitation of inclinometers for the obtention of mooring line tensions.

8.3.3 Global Navigation Satellite Systems

Nowadays there are many floating facilities using GNSS technology, alone or combined with inertial sensors, for monitoring and measuring their position and attitude [183]. The sensor is relatively cheap (depending on performance) and provides very useful information. For instance, it has been used in some cases to detect failures in the mooring lines by finding abnormal motions derived from the broken element (e.g. unexpected offset from equilibrium position and heading) in combination with monitoring the environmental conditions on site (including the wind, currents and waves direction) [187]. The effectiveness of using offset monitoring to detect mooring line failure depends upon many factors, such as the characteristics of the mooring system, water depth, monitoring of environmental conditions and reliability of localisation sensors. Therefore, the relationship between the position and mooring line load needs to be carefully studied. Using this technology can also give insight into the accumulated cyclic loading, providing quantitative input to assessing the remaining fatigue-life expectancy.

8.3.4 Integrated Monitoring and Advisory System (IMAS)

Regarding integrated monitoring systems, latest studies have been focused on this technology for real time acquisition of mooring line loads on offshore floating structures. Several attempts have been carried out to monitor and detect mooring line overloading and failure, but so far the effectiveness of the system is still questionable since the technology is relatively new and has been used in a limited number of applications.

The efficiency of the technologies has been approached to know how reliable and mature the current line tension monitoring system is. The most fundamental issue that must be addressed by all of them is the precise need to understand performance between mooring systems and subject platform (e.g., marine corrosion, fatigue tensions, mechanical damage, extreme storm tensions, loss of line). Thus, modelling tools are necessary to improve and it is equally important to interpret the results in a way that is easy to understand [183].

Investment strategy must also be addressed that should be pursued in terms of cost optimization, particularly from the point of view of CAPEX and OPEX indicators.

It seems that mostly stakeholders and operators are realizing the benefits of deploying such a mooring line tension monitoring system for an offshore floating platform, hence, new-build systems now tend to

include this in the design, since a monitoring system is most easily incorporated into a facility at the design and construction phase.

The most challenges are for existing units to be retro-fitted. The cost of retro-fitting not only includes the cost of the monitoring systems, but also the cost of installations, which is often expensive (especially for underwater installation). The cost and the effects of the monitoring system will continue to be a challenging topic [183].

The measurement equipment for a mooring monitoring system is exposed to harsh environments, especially for underwater components. The instrument device is often out of reach for inspections and maintenance. It could be difficult to determine the source of an abnormal signal (e.g. failure of the instrument or the system itself) without redundancy, or a lot of troubleshooting.

A possible solution may be to use multiple monitoring methods, as well as the right balance between maintenance and renewal activities based on robust criteria, such as the average life of equipment and their repairing cost, the localization of the equipment and the various access constraints associated should be studied [183].

8.4 Summary

Several monitoring technologies are available today to provide mooring line tension measurements in floating platforms as a source of information for integrity assessment and management. However, these technologies present several issues related to robustness and reliability, as well as costs if they are to be applied to FOW, where long term operation and low cost are mandatory requirements.

On the other hand, FOW demands a cost-effective and easy to deploy/operate monitoring solution for mooring systems, which is able to work reliably during the whole operational life of the wind farm.

9. Digital Twin (INT)

9.1 Introduction

In recent years O&G companies have strived for continuous improvement due to a combination of drives such as the declining oil price, increasing cost of extracting oil & gas, and ever-increasing project costs. In addition, the ageing of the existing assets brings several challenges that need to be addressed to ensure the assets can continue to produce safely and reliably ensuring the desired level of production can be achieved.

With technology advancing at a fast pace, organisations have to closely look at digitalization and investigate how their business can be improved by using relevant tools, including digital twin. At this regard, the wind industry is also working towards the digitisation of systems and processes. However, early developments in this field such as WindGEMINI (developed by DNV GL) and WindTwin (R&D project lead by Brunel University) are focused on the wind turbine and little attention is being paid to substructures.

A digital twin is a digital representation of a physical asset. This can be presented in various formats for example databases containing design data, Piping and Instrumentation Diagram (P&IDs), drawings, specifications, vendor data or an interactive graphical sophisticated 3D model which allows the user to access information by clicking components within the 3D model.

A digital twin also can be used for monitoring, providing diagnostics and prognostics to optimize asset performance and utilization. Sensory data can be combined with historical data, human expertise and simulations to further improve the prognostic results.

Figure 66 – High level digital twin architecture

A digital twin integrates both engineering data and real-time data from operations, it uses for example SCADA data and PI (Process Information) historian. A digital twin combines all the digital twin building

blocks (described in section 9.2) with the sole objective to improve business performance (safer, faster and cheaper).

The key to this is that analysis can be done based on accurate (engineering and real-time) data to be able to make well informed decisions.

In simplistic term, building a digital twin requires the definition of a digital representation of the key asset component and its associated data, building the interconnection between the component and ensuring the data that is available and/or collected by sensor is available real time. This combined with the right analysis tools can ensure the performance of the asset is monitored real time and therefore informed decision can be taken promptly. An example of digital twin architecture is represented in Figure 66.

9.2 Current Related Technologies

Building a digital twin requires simultaneous utilisation of several technologies/tools which may be available with different levels of maturity. We can refer to these tools as building blocks. Some of these building blocks and the current level of maturity are described, for reference in this section.

9.2.1 3D / 4D / 5D Models

Terminology of 3D and 4D models is quite consistent, but for 5D and even 6D the industries use different definitions. However, generally, the following definitions apply:

- 3D engineering model that is a digital design of the plant
- 4D is a 3D model with a time dimension added to it
- 5D is when an extra dimension is added namely resources (like availability of material)
- 6D is when the cost dimension is added that allow stakeholders to evaluate costs and model cash flows for each phase of construction).

New plant projects often start with a 3D engineering model to design complex plants including piping, equipment, structural (including modelling and integrated analysis), civil/ foundation, electrical cable tray, HVAC ducting, and multi-disciplinary hangers and supports. Several deliverables are generated from a 3D Model tool like isometrics (2D views). Designs can be checked against algorithms and rule-based engineering. These models illustrate a project in a digital form that can then be analysed to determine inconsistencies that would normally not be discovered until the construction phase.

A significant benefit is that data from a 3D model can be processed and used to automate construction activities.

In both geosciences and in construction management a 3D model is used in combination with time/schedule to do step by step analysis, this is called 4D. For construction management for example this is used for construction sequencing and analyse different scenarios. 4D modelling allows stakeholders to visualize construction over the project duration to identify potential spatial/ temporal conflicts in schedule.

Low utilisation of field workers is caused by material not being available due to uncertainty of material location unclear or not arrived at site yet. Adding information about material availability to the engineering and construction data can significantly improve “hands-on-tool” time of construction engineers. This is called 5D.

Overall, 3D models are common in many industries.

9.2.2 Laser Scanning

Laser Scanning is a non-contact, non-destructive technology that digitally captures the shape of existing physical objects using a line of laser light. 3D laser scanners create point clouds of data from the surface of an object. It is a way to capture a physical object’s exact size and shape into a digital 3D

representation. Besides, these 3D models can then be layered with additional data and linked to the real-life asset by means of sensors, via the cloud.

9.2.3 Photogrammetry

Photogrammetry is the science of making measurements from photographs, especially for recovering the exact positions of surface points. In the application of offshore and subsea assets, 3D models can be generated from a series of GPS enabled digital pictures taken with a camera. As with Laser Scanning the 3D models can be layered with data and linked back to the asset by means of sensors, via the cloud.

9.2.4 Cloud Services

Cloud computing is an Information Technology (IT) paradigm, a model for enabling universal access to shared pools of configurable resources such as computer networks, servers, storage, applications and services.

Cloud computing allows companies to avoid or minimize up-front IT infrastructure costs. As well, third-party clouds enable organisations to focus on their core businesses instead of expending resources on computer infrastructure and maintenance. It also allows enterprises to get their applications up and running faster, with improved manageability and less maintenance, and that it enables IT teams to more rapidly adjust resources to meet fluctuating and unpredictable business demand.

9.2.5 Internet of Things (IoT)

The Internet of things (IoT) is the network of physical devices, vehicles, and other items embedded with electronics, software, sensors, actuators, and network connectivity which enable these objects to collect and exchange data.

The IoT allows objects to be sensed or controlled remotely across existing network infrastructure, creating opportunities for more direct integration of the physical world into computer-based systems, and resulting in improved efficiency, accuracy and economic benefit in addition to reduced human intervention. When IoT is augmented with sensors and actuators, the technology becomes an instance of the more general class of cyber-physical systems, which also encompasses technologies such as smart grids, virtual power plants, smart homes, intelligent transportation and smart cities.

The cloud is an essential part of a Digital Twin and is the fundamental storage location and processing capability for the digital data and applications

9.2.6 Artificial Intelligence (AI) & Machine Learning

Artificial intelligence is apparently intelligent behaviour by machines, rather than the natural intelligence of humans and other animals. Artificial Intelligence is the broader concept of machines being able to carry out tasks in a way that we would consider “smart”.

Machine learning is a method of data analysis that automates analytical model building. Using algorithms that iteratively learn from data it allows computers to find hidden insights without being explicitly programmed where to look. Machine Learning is a current application of AI based around the idea that we should be able to give machines access to data and let them learn for themselves.

9.2.7 Big Data

Generally, Big data is term for data sets that are so large or complex that traditional data processing application software is inadequate to deal with them. The term can also be used to refer to the use of predictive analytics, user behaviour analytics, or certain other advanced data analytics methods that extract value from data, and seldom to a size of data set.

Data sets grow rapidly because they are increasingly gathered by cheap and numerous information-sensing 'Internet of things' devices such as mobile devices, UAV's, cameras, software logs, and wireless sensor networks.

9.2.8 Sensors & Actuators

Sensors and actuators have become more affordable and available, which ensures ubiquitous presence of versatile sensors and subsequent data acquisition using computer networks. Data analysis based on control of resources or physical environments is more possible than ever before. Physical systems collect sensory information from the real world and send them to the digital twin. The Digital twin computation modules would process this data and notify the physical systems about the findings, sometimes send control commands to make necessary changes in the physical world or reconfigure system parameters, if required.

9.2.9 Advanced Analytics

Analytics are becoming more advanced relative to the evolution of Digital Twin. These analytics can be used to model the present and past state of every asset in a Digital Twin environment. These analytics include, but not limited to;

- Thermal
- Mechanical
- Electrical
- Fluid Dynamics
- Material
- Economic
- Statistical

A combination of real-time and historic data can be used and combined to perform advanced analytics by means of algorithms and machine learning. The results can be used in various operational scenarios.

9.3 Numerical models

Numerical models are an essential component of digital twin. Numerical models use mathematical models to represent in an approximate way the behaviour of a physical model, generally over time. There are several engineering tools that are able to perform numerical simulations. The MooringSense digital twin will use numerical models to:

- (a) Predict platform motions in waves, wind and current;
- (b) Predict mooring line tension;
- (c) Predict the degradation and aging of chains and synthetic ropes and the remaining lifetime of the mooring lines.

The following paragraphs describe the state of the art on these topics.

9.3.1 Platform motions and mooring line tensions

Mooring line tension is the essential information the SHM system of MooringSense will extract from a numerical model, solving the coupled dynamic problem of the FOW in waves, wind and current. Finite element methods (FEM) and lumped mass methods are the most popular for solving mooring line dynamics and to calculate the related tensions. Prediction of line tensions for chain and steel wire ropes are quite accurate, provided the forcing motions at the fairleads are correct (there are challenges for synthetic ropes, as described further ahead).

The project will use state-of-the computer-aided engineering (CAE) tools to calculate the aeroelastic responses of horizontal axis wind turbines (FAST and RIFLEX). These numerical tools join

aerodynamics models, hydrodynamics models for offshore structures, control and electrical system (servo) dynamic models, and structural (elastic) dynamic models to enable coupled nonlinear aero-hydro-servo-elastic simulation in the time domain. The aerodynamic models use wind-inflow data and solve for the rotor-wake effects and blade-element aerodynamic loads, including dynamic stall. Overall, one can say that prediction of the floater motions in wind, waves and current are still subjected to quite large uncertainty, especially in high sea-states. Presently, the uncertainty in the calculation of mooring loads is mostly related to the prediction of the platform low frequency (LF) motions.

The floaters of floating wind turbines for many of the proposed concepts may be considered large volume structures, since the characteristic of floater dimensions are on the order of magnitude of the typical wave lengths. This means the hydrodynamic wave loads are within the diffraction wave force regime, where inertia effects dominate and viscous effects (drag) are of lesser importance. Depending on the concept and on the representative wavelengths, it might be that the hydrodynamic forces are given by a contribution from potential flow inertia forces and a contribution from viscous drag. Wave loads on large volume structures can be calculated by Green function panel methods based on potential flow theory, which solves the radiation/diffraction problem (see for example [188] and [189]). If the first order problem is solved, one obtains the liner excitation and responses and the second order mean wave drift force coefficients. If the problem is solved up to the second order for pairs of harmonic incident waves, then the wave excitation includes also difference frequency components, related to low frequency forces, and sum frequency components, related to sum frequency forces.

Radiation/diffraction codes usually provide quite good prediction of the wave frequency motions, even for severe sea-states. However, if the natural periods of the motions (heave, roll, pitch) are within the wave frequency range and the potential flow damping is small, one usually needs to add some damping which represents viscous effects to achieve an accurate prediction of the resonant motions.

On the other hand, it has been demonstrated that standard radiation/diffraction analysis under-predicts the low frequency motions of semi-submersibles in high sea states. The main reason is viscous wave drift, which is neglected by the standard analysis. The same is observed for FPSOs under certain conditions, although the origin of the discrepancies is different. The EXWAVE JIP (Joint Industry Project), ran from 2015 to 2017, with the objective of improving methods, procedures and standard industry practice in design prediction of extreme mooring line loads (Fonseca 2017a, 2017b, 2017c) [190][191][192]. The focus was on the prediction of low frequency wave excitation, including wave-current interaction effects. The JIP proposes methods to improve calculation of mooring line loads, including:

- (a) A semi-empirical method to account viscous wave drift.
- (b) A method to account for additional wave drift forces due to wave frequency viscous effects.
- (c) Account for wave-current interaction effects in the wave drift forces.
- (d) Practical methods to calculate wave drift forces based on full quadratic transfer functions (QTFs), instead of applying Newman's approximation.

The present project will implement the procedures recommended by the Exwave JIP for improving calculation of mooring line tensions.

9.3.2 Statics and dynamics analysis of synthetic fibre ropes

Synthetic fibre ropes have a number of advantages for the mooring of FWTs. Their lightweight (approximately weightless in water), high strength and varying elasticity properties results in high performance mooring systems which for example: are easy to install, minimise dynamic and fatigue loading on structures and other mooring components and ensure reliable station keeping for the full life cycle of the project. The state of the art in synthetic mooring is the use of polyester continuous filament fibre ropes, which have a long track record in O&G (more than 30 years). Whilst this

technology may still have some relevance in FWT mooring a number of researchers have identified the need to consider alternative materials [193] such as: HMPE, Aramid, Nylon, etc. to respond to the specific requirements of FOW (e.g. long term operation, special loading characteristics), in different scenarios (i.e. shallow, intermediate and deep water application) and for different configurations (mainly taut and semi-taut).

The most suitable and promising solutions depending on design configurations and site conditions are:

- Shallow locations and semi-sub/spar/barge: Polyester and Nylon
- Deep water locations and TLP: HMPE, Aramid, and other stiff materials

Compared to chain and wire ropes, synthetic ropes are characterized by more complex nonlinear axial stiffness properties which are a function of applied load (mean load, load range, frequency) and load history. As a consequence of this complex behaviour, numerical modelling of synthetic rope axial stiffness is still challenging and in practice, this means that mooring analysis cannot rely on one material stiffness value. The state of the art in the oil and gas industry (e.g. FP(S)O mooring with polyester) is to undertake project specific test campaigns using the rope design selected for the project. This practise is slow, expensive and allows little flexibility in the design process. The majority of data available on the stiffness characteristics of mooring lines is assessed in the context of oil and gas mooring system parameters. However, FWT mooring parameters are not the same as oil and gas mooring parameters (due to smaller floater sizes, wind turbine induced loads, shallower mooring depths and redundancy requirements) and so existing data for mooring lines will be of limited relevance to FWT systems. Consequently, there is a need to capture mooring line data relevant to FOW systems for a range of mooring line types. Ideally this would be done with parameters that could be applied to multiple projects. For example, the use of nylon is considered especially interesting for FOW in shallow waters due to its high elasticity, but since there is concern over traditional nylon fatigue performance it has only been used in oil and gas short deployments. However new nylon mooring line constructions seem that may provide a suitable solution for the long operation of FOW farms. Qualification of such materials is expected to allow their future application.

The usual approach for mooring analysis with respect to axial stiffness is to use the upper bound axial stiffness for calculation of extreme tensions and the lower bound stiffness for horizontal offsets. This approach is conservative and not accurate enough for the requirements of the MooringSense system functionalities (e.g. virtual tension monitoring, SHM, etc.). More accurate methods may be applied, provided, first, the synthetic rope dynamic stiffness properties are known and, second, the numerical code for line dynamics is able to model the complex dynamic stiffness.

Regarding numerical modelling of the complex dynamic stiffness, SINTEF Ocean implemented a new time domain nonlinear spring-dashpot model to represent, simultaneously, the recoverable instantaneous elongation, the slow elongation response, the irreversible instantaneous elongation and the long-term elongation – creep [194]. The lines are represented by finite elements, which means that a new element incorporating the aforementioned characteristics was implemented. Such models require careful calibration against actual test data. In this respect, the 6 CILP method [195], [196], [197] (CILP: change in length properties) provides a systematic framework to characterise the tension and stretch characteristics of synthetic mooring lines according to 6 parameters, which can be identified with pre-defined laboratory tests. In this way a theoretical model can be built and calibrated with laboratory data that is applicable to multiple FWT mooring system types and configurations. Additional mooring line types may easily be added to the numerical model, at a later stage, by following the same procedures and acquiring new test data.

Additional information on the mechanical properties of synthetic ropes and proposed numerical models can be consulted in [198], [199], [200]. Other relevant publications on ageing based on fatigue tests [201], axial compression fatigue [202], axial stiffness and damping for nylon 6 parallel stranded ropes [203], and the influence of aging on rope performance [205] are available.

9.4 Gap Analysis

Even though the concept of Digital Twin is not new, its development and implementation in FOW substructures is still a challenge, especially in the field of numerical modelling. While there is a wide range of Digital Twin associated technologies such as IoT, Cloud services, sensors, data analytics or big data, which are already available for the industry, the development of high-fidelity virtual models requires further research and development. For instance, the development of a useful virtual model of the mooring system of a FOWT, capable of reproducing accurately and reliably performance under any existing environmental/operational condition and for the whole operation life, is still a real challenge. At this regard, significant improvements are needed in several fields:

- Prediction of floater motions under high sea states are subjected to significant uncertainties. In fact, a significant underestimation of motions has been identified in the bibliography.
- Degradation, damages and stiffness changes in the mooring lines require a better understanding in order to allow a proper numerical modelling.

9.5 Summary

Designing and implementing a Digital Twin of a mooring system requires the simultaneous adoption of several technologies and tools. Some of these technologies and the respective levels of maturity have been described in the above sections, however technologies and tools are evolving at fast pace and therefore it is important to stay up to date with these developments.

On the other hand, one of the major challenges, when building a digital twin is to develop the system architecture and to ensure seamless trouble-free communication between all building blocks. In addition to this the level of understanding required to develop high-fidelity virtual models capable of accurate and reliable output is significant.

Finally, the development of Digital Twin technology for mooring systems implies several challenges. Areas where improvement is most apparent include the understanding of degradation, damage and stiffness to mooring lines and the ability to predict motion under high sea states. For the MooringSense project, the proposed digital twin architecture will be defined in deliverable D2.4.

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